

{Möbius strips}: Sides, Sheets and Orientations

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Abstract

The one-sheeted, one-sided, π rad twist *{Möbius strip}*, that in the literature is the epitome of a non-orientable surface, and some related *{2-Manifolds}* are analyzed, each one by its *{Intrinsic Observer}*, according to an abstract point of view. It is shown that it is not necessary to cut a *{Möbius strip}* somehow in order to render it orientable.

Notation

{ } for Spacetime Objects, Sets; [] for closed Manifolds; () for open Manifolds, Events, States.
Side {S i} *hindered Transition*, {S h} Side. Sheet {s p} *permitted Transition*, {s q} Sheet.
Oriented {i} on an Oriented Curve: $\{\rightarrow i\} = \{\text{to } i\}$; $\{\rightarrow i\} \in \{i\}$; $\{i \rightarrow\} = \{\text{from } i\}$; $\{i \rightarrow\} \in \{i\}$.
n.b.h. = neighborhood; n.b.h.s = neighborhoods; N.B.H.s = neighborhoods, in:
“Perception N.B.H.s” = “Superposed n.b.h.s.” \supset “Reception n.b.h.”.
“Perception N.B.H.” = “Reception n.b.h.” only for a one-sheeted one-sided *{2-Manif. with boundary}*.
For States: the first subscript is spatial, the second subscript is temporal.
($u \times v$) = “A Point that is expressed by two coordinate values”.
Along the Rulings of a Ruled Surface: $\{\|\mathbf{V}\|\} = \{\text{Field of Segments}\}$. $\{[\mathbf{V}]\} = \{\text{Field of Vectors}\}$.
{Fundamental Polygon Edge Arrows} for the Oriented Edges of a *{Fundamental Polygon}*.
{Induced Orientation Arrows} for a *{Polygonally decomposed Surface}* [21].
{Maker-applied Arrows} applied to the Curves of a Surface.
{Internal Half Edge} = “the part of an *{Edge}* that the *{Intrinsic Observer}* can contact and sense” [1]. She cannot contact and sense an *{External Half Edge}*.
Here: *{Half Vectors}*, *{Lengthwise Half Edges}*, *{Widthwise Half Edges}* are lengthwise-splitted.

1 Preliminaries

1.1) Some ambient and abstract *{Manifolds with boundary}* are the arguments of this study. “Abstract” means analyzed according to the Statement 1.3 below.

1.2) *{Manifolds with boundary}* are the objects of study, but the insistence here on their *{Observers}* is due to the fact that the gathered data and the ensuing definitions are *{Observer}*-dependent.

1.3) Different Analysts of an Object have different concepts of it and formulate different descriptions, here with distinct symbols for clarity.

1.4) An *{Extrinsic Observer}*-defined *{Fundamental Polygon}*, a.k.a. *{Singular topological polygon}* ([21] page 5) and its *{Labelling Scheme}* ([18] page 449) are not concepts of an *{Intrinsic Observer}*.

1.5) **{Bare Manifold with boundary}**: without an adjoined Structure. In the literature it is called a “Shape”.

1.6) **Adjoined Structure to a {Bare Manifold with boundary}**. The “Structure” is assumed associated with the {Bare Manifold w.b.}, when the *{Intrinsic Observer}* explores and describes the {Structured Manif. w.b.}, a.k.a. {parametrized Manif. w.b.}. That is: the considered Structure is completed before the analysis. A Structure is a set of *adjoined and fixed* to the {Bare Manif. w.b.} implements, say: partitions, fields, a metric, charts i.e. a coordinate system, a set of parameters. polynomials, angles, orders, directions, orientations, boundaries, layers, patterns, figures, textures, colors, hue, tags, marks. Intrinsic reference submanifolds: points, curves, surfaces. Maps, functions, etc. With the literature’s concepts: the *allowing calculus Smooth Structure*, and *Non-smooth Structure*.

1.6.1) Many possible Parametrizations for a Manifold’s Structure. To be considered too: non-parametrized Manifolds , non-parametrized Submanifolds.

1.6.2) By the above: the Structure is *intrinsic* to the {Structured Manif. w.b.}.

1.6.3) Structure: a necessary intrusion for understanding and description.

1.6.4) A *suitable* Structure must avoid uncertainties in the definition of the {param. Manif. w.b.}. E. g., in the definition of its Extension and Boundary.

1.6.5) **Statement 1.1.** A *Structure covering no more than the analyzed {Structured Manif. w.b.} within its specified limits*, is operatively preferable. In a {Structured Manif. w.b.} with cyclic features and a specified number of cycles, a *suitable* Structure covers exactly this No. of cycles. (A Structure covering the analyzed {Structured Manif. w.b.} in excess may be misleading).

1.6.6) A Structure may have discontinuities.

1.6.7) A Structure creates distinctions: it divides the analyzed {param. Manif. w.b.}: Interior, Boundary, Neighborhoods, Sides, Sheets, Edges, Aspects, . . .

1.6.8) By the adjoined Structure, the {Structured Manif. w.b.} is no more the original {Bare Manif. w.b.}: the usual, transforming, “Observation effect”.

1.6.9) It is assumed here that the Maker adjoined the Structure to the {Bare Manif. w.b.}, choosing it in a set of suitable Structures. (Only in special cases the *{Intrinsic Observer}* contributes; normally her task being limited to the analysis. To avoid complications, only one definer of the Structure).

1.6.10) **Statement 1.2.** The *{Intrinsic Observer} must distinguish properties of the underlying {Bare Manif. w.b.}, (that, we say, is a specimen of a {topological Manif. w.b.}), and properties of the adjoined Structure*.

1.6.11) An *{Intrinsic Observer}* analyzes only the {Structured Manif. w.b.}. ([24], [25]) to which she is applied. She cannot have an idea of Manifolds’ classes.

1.6.12) **{Associates}** \equiv { *{Intrinsic Observer}*, *{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}*, *{Observation Implement}*, *{Instruments}*, . . . }. They do not pertain to the {Structured Manif. w.b.}, since they are not pure Geometric Objects; they operate in Spacetime. They need positioning, adaptation, operation. They enter into the argument since not only a specified {Reference Space} is necessary, but also a specified Analyst and her Devices for comparisons and measures.

1.7) **Modalities.** Sect. III deals with a bimodal { *{Intrinsic Observer}* }_X, { *{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}* }_χ, who was introduced here, without incur-

ring in the cumbersome excess of a multimodal $\{Intrinsic Observer\}$. An $\{Intrinsic Observer\}_X$ analyzes a $\{\text{param. 2-Manif. w.b.}\} = X$ relatively to X , with specified sensing modalities. A $\{Powerful Intrinsic Observer\}_X$ analyzes a $\{\text{param. 2-Manif. w.b.}\} = \mathcal{X}$ relatively to \mathcal{X} , with - different from the preceding - sensing modalities. Obviously, different modalities imply differently sensed, named, described $\{\text{param. Manifolds w.b.}\}$.

1.8) **{Reference Space} = {Structured Manif. w.b.}**.

1.8.1) **{Complement Space}** $_X$ of X is conceived, not directly sensed, by a Theorist $\{Intrinsic Observer\}_X$, because here it is assumed not emitting Signals.

1.8.2) **{AmbientSpace}** = $\{\text{Reference Space}\} \cup \{\text{Associates}\} \cup \{\text{Complement Space}\}$.

1.9) **{Boundary}** $_X$ according to an $\{Extrinsic Observer\}_X$, contains $\{\text{Edges}\}_X$.

$\{\text{Edge}\}_X = \{\{\text{Half Edge}\}_X \cup \{\text{Half Edge}\}_{\{\text{Complement Space}\}_X}\}$. With the orientation: \mathcal{X} , $\{\text{Half Edge}\}_X$, $\{\text{Half Edge}\}_{\{\text{Complement Space}\}_X}$, $\{\text{Complement Space}\}_X$.

1.9.1) **{Intrinsic Boundary}** $_X$. For X , and similarly for \mathcal{X} . It is not the $\{Extrinsic Observer\}_X$'s $\{\text{Boundary}\}_X$. The $\{\text{Intrinsic Boundary}\}_X$ is what the $\{Intrinsic Observer\}_X$ senses as such. She may sense:

a) The **{Half Edges}** $_X$. (She does not sense the $\{\text{Half Edges}\}_{\{\text{Complement Space}\}_X}$, that is towards the $\{\text{Complement Space}\}_X$).

b) The $\{Intrinsic Observer\}_X$ knows that a **Non-smooth {Half Edge}** $_X$ does not allow Transitions; it is associated to discontinuities, either of the $\{\text{Bare Manif. w.b.}\}$ or of the $\{\text{Structure}\}_X$.

c) **{Internal Edges}** $_X$. They are delimiters, either of the extension of X , or of its Regions_X . The $\{Intrinsic Observer\}_X$ dubs Smooth an $\{\text{Internal Edge}\}_X$ since it allows Transitions. (Otherwise, it is not an $\{\text{Internal Edge}\}$). A strong $\{\text{Parametric Continuity}\}$ between its adjacent Regions. Then the $\{Intrinsic Observer\}_X$ senses: $\{\text{Half Internal Edge}\}_{\text{Region 1}} \cup \{\text{Half Internal Edge}\}_{\text{Region 2}}$.

1.9.2) **Example 1.1.** α) An $\{Extrinsic Observer\}_X$ senses $\{\text{Region 1}\}_X$, $\{\text{Region 2}\}_X$ in Contact, due to the absence of intermediate $\{\text{Complement Space}\}_X$, but in a Non-smooth Contact, due to their opposite $\{\text{Circ. Arrows}\}$.

β) The $\{Intrinsic Observer\}_X$ at $\{\text{Region 1}\}_X$ senses $\{\text{Region 1}\}_X$ with its Non-smooth $\{\text{Half Edge}\}_{\text{Region 1}}$, and, after her displacement within X , she senses $\{\text{Region 2}\}_X$ with its Non-smooth $\{\text{Half Edge}\}_{\text{Region 2}}$. She cannot sense outside X , so she cannot sense the $\{\text{Contact: Region 1, Region 2}\}$, since it is in a Space that is not X .

γ) The $\{Powerful Intrinsic Observer\}_X$ at $\{\text{Region 1}\}_X$ senses $\{\text{Region 1}\}_X$ with its Non-smooth $\{\text{Half Edge}\}_{\text{Region 1}}$. After her displacement within \mathcal{X} , she senses $\{\text{Region 2}\}_X$ with its Non-smooth $\{\text{Half Edge}\}_{\text{Region 2}}$. Also, in both places she senses the non-smooth Contact of the two Regions., in a Space that is not \mathcal{X} .

1.10) **Transitions.** A here considered $\{\text{Transition}\}$ is between two Regions. a) For the **Observer**, from one Region to another, either a shift of position, or a shift of analysis, or both. b) For **Calculus**, a $\{\text{Transition Map}\}$ between two Regions [14]: the comparison of the Regions' partial derivatives of some order. Smooth / Non-smooth Transitions: Continuity / Discontinuity is assessed. [13]

1.11) **Superposition.** Elements of a $\{\text{Space 1}\}$ can be superposed in a $\{\text{Space 2}\}$.

1.11.1) **Example 1.2.** The Points $\beta(a)$, $\beta(b)$ are distinct in the $\{\text{Space 2}\}$

= Curve $\beta(\ell)$ that is a self-intersecting Subspace of $\{\text{Space } 2\} = X$ Surface; $\beta(a)$, $\beta(b)$ are superposed in X . The $\{\text{Intrinsic Observer}\}_X$ considers distinct Points $\beta(a)$, $\beta(b)$ in the Curve $\beta(\ell)$, since their ℓ -values are different: $a \neq b$, and Superposition in X , since on $\{\text{Chart}\}_X$: $x^i(a) = x^i(b)$; $i = \{1, 2\}$.

1.11.2) **Superposition of Elements of a $\{\text{Perception N.B.H.s}\}$.** For the $\{\text{Sensed together at one $\{\text{Reception n.b.h.}\}$ and including it, mentally separable i.e. distinguishable, N.B.H.s}\}$.

1.12) **Partition of a $\{\text{Structured 2-Manif. w.b.}\}$.** Here it is an $\{\text{Intrinsic Observer}\}_X$'s mental separation of X into a set $\{\text{Submanifolds of } X\}$. Similarly a $\{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}_X$'s for \mathcal{X} .

1.12.1) Here encountered classes of Subsurfaces of a Surface (in particular: a Strip): **Sheets, Sides, Aspects, n.b.h.s, N.B.H.s**.

Abstract definitions for said Subsurfaces are introduced. [5]

1.12.2) For the same Surface, two sets: **$\{\text{Sheets}\}$, $\{\text{Sides}\}$** . Each set covers the assumed Surface entirely.

1.13) **Intrinsic Sheetness of a Surface. Superposition** is the definer of the stack, dubbed **$\{\text{Sheets}\}$** , of *superposed*, and eventually in series, Subsurfaces. Intrinsic Sheetness may be a local concept: a $\{\text{Reception n.b.h.}\}$ can have a numerous set of *superposed* $\{\text{Perception N.B.H.s}\}$. Intrinsic Sheetness may be a global concept: a set of $\{\text{Reception n.b.h.s}\}$ can have a set of *superposed*, obviously somehow correlated, $\{\text{Perception N.B.H.s}\}$.

1.13.1) **$\{\text{Intrinsic one-Sheetness}\}_X$** of X , for the $\{\text{Intrinsic Observer}\}_X$, who, for definition, has not the ability of perceiving Superpositions, so that for her X is one-sheeted anyway. **$\{\text{Intrinsic one-Sheetness}\}_X$** for a $\{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}_X$ when she does not sense Superpositions in \mathcal{X} .

1.13.2) **$\{\text{Intrinsic multi-Sheetness}\}_X$** according to a $\{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}_X$, sensing \mathcal{X} with a numerous set of *superposed, eventually also structured in series* $\{\text{Sheets}\}_X$.

1.13.3) **$\{\text{Charts}\}$** . Each parametrized $\{\text{Sheet}\}$ has its subset $\{\text{Charts}\}$. Possibly each $\{\text{Sheet}\}$ has one single, Sheet-filling $\{\text{Chart}\}$. Obviously no $\{\text{Chart}\}$ for a $\{\text{Sheet}\}$ without $\{\text{Parametrization}\}$.

1.13.4) The $\{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}_X$, distinguishing the Sheets of a Stack, performs a **Mental decomposition of \mathcal{X} into $\{\text{Sheets}\}_X$** .

An easy decomposition, if each $\{\text{Sheet}_i\}$ has its own single $\{\text{Chart}_i\}$.

At a $\{\text{Reception n.b.h.}\}$: distinction of $\{\text{Sheets}\}$ by sensing the corresponding set $\{\text{Superposed n.b.h.s}\}$.

1.14) **Intrinsic Sidedness of a Surface.** I.e. an intrinsically defined set of Subsurfaces dubbed **$\{\text{Sides}\}$** . They are superposed and/or in series. **Transition** is the definer. Smooth Transitions within each $\{\text{Side}\}$ and entirely Non-smooth Transitions among $\{\text{Sides}\}$. For example, $\{\text{Intrinsic Observer}\}$, $\{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}$ sense Non-smooth Transitions at a sharp change of Curvature.

1.14.1) **Intrinsic one-Sidedness.** It is sensed by the $\{\text{Intrinsic Observer}\}_X$ in X having available some Smooth Transitions, or by the $\{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}_X$ in \mathcal{X} having available some Smooth Transitions. No sensation of other $\{\text{Sides}\}$.

1.14.2) **Intrinsic multi-Sidedness.** a) An $\{Intrinsic Observer\}_X$ cannot perform Non-smooth Transitions, and cannot directly sense, outside its unique $\{Side\}_X = X$. Hence she does not sense $\{Intrinsic\ multi-Sidedness\}$. b) A $\{Powerful\ Intrinsic\ Observer\}_X$ cannot travel entirely a multi-sided \mathcal{X} , since she cannot make non-smooth Transitions. She remains in her $\{Residence\ Side\} \subset \mathcal{X}$. Multi-sidedness of \mathcal{X} , if she directly senses, not only conceives, many $\{Sides\}_X$. She performs a **Mental decomposition of \mathcal{X} into $\{Sides\}_X$.**

1.14.3) a) $\{Analysis\ Space\}_X = \{ \{Intrinsic\ Observer\}_X, X = \{unique\ Side\ of\ X\} = \{Residence\ Side\ in\ X\}, \dots \}$. The $\{Intrinsic\ Observer\}_X$ cannot go out of her $\{Residence\ Side\ in\ X\} = X$. She cannot get information outside it. b) $\{Analysis\ Space\}_X = \{ \{Powerful\ Intrinsic\ Observer\}_X, \mathcal{X} = \{Sides\}_X \supset \{Residence\ Side\ in\ \mathcal{X}\}, \dots \}$. The $\{Powerful\ Intrinsic\ Observer\}_X$ cannot go out of her $\{Residence\ Side\ in\ \mathcal{X}\}$. In the case of $\{Multi-sidedness\}_X$, the $\{ \{Powerful\ Intrinsic\ Observer\}_X \}$'s travelled space of \mathcal{X} = its $\{Residence\ Side\ in\ \mathcal{X}\} < \mathcal{X}$ and an imperfect coupling: Surface \mathcal{X} , $\{Powerful\ Intrinsic\ Observer\}_X$.

1.14) **Example 1.3.** \mathcal{X} has two precisely superposed Sheets, with distinguishable $\{Structures\}$. Each $\{Sheet\}_i$ has its own $\{Intrinsic\ Boundary\}_i$. Non-smooth Transitions of the superposed $\{Intrinsic\ Boundaries\}$, so that this case implies: each $\{Sheet\}_i$ is $\{Side\}_i$. The Maker dubbed them $\{S1s1\}, \{S2s2\}$. He gave \mathcal{X} an Orientation: $\{Circ.\ Arrow\ field\}_X = \{ \{Circ.\ Arrow\ subfield\}_{\{S1s1\}}, \{Circ.\ Arrow\ subfield\}_{\{S2s2\}} \}$. The $\{Powerful\ Intrinsic\ Observer\}_X$ at her $\{Residence\ Side\}$, say $\{S1s1\}$, perceives: $\{S1s1\}$ with $\{Circ.\ Arrow\ subfield\}_{\{S1s1\}}$ and Verso $\{S2s2\}$ with $\{Circ.\ Arrow\ subfield\}_{Verso\ \{S2s2\}}$; a Superposition.

1.15) **Statement 1.3.** Obviously a Manifold is here dubbed one-sheeted, or one sided, only if its specified Observer directly senses (not only conceives) that.

1.16) **{Neighborhood} a.k.a. {n.b.h.}**. It is a small not pointlike Subsurface. If a Parametrization exists, it expresses the $\{n.b.h.\}$: Position, Directions, Orientations, $\{Circ.\ Arrow\}$, ... In absence of a Parametrization, if the Surface can be traversed by its $\{Intrinsic\ Observer\}$ or its $\{Powerful\ Intrinsic\ Observer\}$: Touch, measured gen. curvatures, positioned Marks specify it.

1.17) **{Reception n.b.h.}**. A $\{n.b.h.\} = \Delta X_u \subset X$ takes the name $\{Reception\ n.b.h.\}$ if it is received by the state $(Intrinsic\ Observer_{ut})_X @ \Delta X_u$, who lies and senses there. A $\{n.b.h.\} = \Delta \mathcal{X}_u \subset \mathcal{X}$ takes the name $\{Reception\ n.b.h.\}$ if it is received by the state $(Powerful\ Intrinsic\ Observer_{ut})_X @ \Delta \mathcal{X}_u$, who lies and senses there.

1.17.1) **Globally.** In an ordered analysis, the $\{Intrinsic\ Observer\}_X$ perceives X as an ordered Succession $\{ \{Perception\ N.B.H.s\} \}_X$.

1.17.2) **Globally.** In an ordered analysis, the $\{Powerful\ Intrinsic\ Observer\}_X$ perceives \mathcal{X} as an ordered Succession $\{ \{Perception\ N.B.H.s\} \}_X$.

1.18) **{Perception N.B.H.s}**. It is a Stack $\{N.B.H.s\}$.

1.18.1) For an $(Intrinsic\ Observer_{ut})_X @ \Delta X_u$: $\{Perception\ N.B.H.\}_{\Delta X_u} = \{Reception\ n.b.h.\} = \Delta X_u$. $(Intrinsic\ Observer_{ut})_X$ contains an $\{Image\}$ of it.

1.18.2) For a $(Powerful\ Intrinsic\ Observer_{ut})_X @ \Delta \mathcal{X}_u$: the $\{Perception\ N.B.H.s\}_{\Delta \mathcal{X}_u} \subset \mathcal{X}$ is the subset of Neighborhoods that are sensed at the same $\{Reception$

- n.b.h.} = $\Delta\mathcal{X}_u$. (*Powerful Intrinsic Observer* u_t) \mathcal{X} contains an {Image} of it.
- 1.18.3) {Perception N.B.H.s} $_{\Delta\mathcal{X}_u}$ = { {Superposed N.B.H.s}, {Glanced N.B.H.s} } $_{\Delta\mathcal{X}_u}$.
- 1.18.4) { **Superposed N.B.H.s** } $_{\Delta\mathcal{X}_u} \supset$ { **Reception n.b.h.** } = $\Delta\mathcal{X}_u$.
- 1.18.5) A definition. The { **Glanced N.B.H.s** } $_{\Delta\mathcal{X}_u}$ a.k.a. { Side-looked N.B.H.s } are adjacent in \mathcal{X} to the {Reception n.b.h.} = $\Delta\mathcal{X}_u$.
- 1.18.6) **Example 1.4.** Two-sheeted, one-sided \mathcal{X} . Local Correspondence: the state (*Powerful Intrinsic Observer* $u_i t$) $\mathcal{X} @ \Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$, {Reception n.b.h.} = $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$, {Perception N.B.H.s}: {Superposed N.B.H.s} = { $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$, Verso $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_s}$ }; {Glanced N.B.H.s} = { $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_g}$, $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_w}$, ..., Verso $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_q}$, Verso $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_p}$, ... }.
- 1.19) **Aspects.** The {*Intrinsic Observer*} and the {*Powerful Intrinsic Observer*} perceive and describe globally a specified Element of her Surface by its Intrinsic {Aspects}, i.e. a set {N.B.H.s} with common, distinguishing, associating properties.
- 1.19.1) In the case of a one-sheeted one-sided X and its {*Intrinsic Observer*} \mathcal{X} . For any ΔX_{u_i} there is the unique {Reception n.b.h.} = ΔX_{u_i} at which ΔX_{u_i} is sensed by the {*Intrinsic Observer*} \mathcal{X} . Set{Aspects} = unique {Aspect} = ΔX_{u_i} .
- 1.19.2) In the case of a one-sheeted one-sided \mathcal{X} and its {*Powerful Intrinsic Observer*} \mathcal{X} . For any $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$ there is the unique {Reception n.b.h.} = $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$, at which $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$ is sensed by the {*Powerful Intrinsic Observer*} \mathcal{X} . Set {Aspects} = unique {Aspect} = { $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$ } = $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$.
- 1.19.3) In the case of a n-sheeted \mathcal{X} , n>1 and its (*Powerful Intr. Observer*) \mathcal{X} . {Correspondence: {Reception n.b.h.s} = { $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$, $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_s}$, $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_h}$, Verso $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_k}$ }. {Aspects} = { $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$, Verso $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$, Glanced $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$, Glanced Verso $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$ }. Where: $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$ is sensed by the state (*Powerful Intrinsic Observer* $u_i t$) $\mathcal{X} @ \Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$. Verso $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$ is sensed by the state (*Powerful Intrinsic Observer* $u_s t'$) $\mathcal{X} @ \Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_s}$, with Superposition: $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_s}$, Verso $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$. Glanced $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$ is sensed by a state (*Powerful Intrinsic Observer* $u_h t'$) $\mathcal{X} @ \Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_h}$. Glanced Verso $\Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_i}$ is sensed by a state (*Powerful Intrinsic Observer* $u_k t''$) $\mathcal{X} @ \Delta\mathcal{X}_{u_k}$.
- 1.19.4) **Example 1.5. Aspects of an Element.**
On the one-sided Surface {MM} \supset {M}, {M2} Sheets.
The (*Powerful Intrinsic Observer* $u_r t$) $\{\text{MM}\} @ \Delta M_{u_r}$ on {M} senses: ΔM_{u_r} .
The (*Powerful Intrinsic Observer* $u_s t'$) $\{\text{MM}\} @ \Delta M2_{u_s}$ on {M2} senses: Verso ΔM_{u_r} .
Element { ΔM_{u_r} } = { ΔM_{u_r} , Verso ΔM_{u_r} } Set of Aspects in {MM}.
- 1.20) **Generalized Curvatures of a {Surface}**. By her body's Derivative Sensors, the {*Intrinsic Observer*} \mathcal{X} or the {*Powerful Intrinsic Observer*} \mathcal{X} can get, step by step, the Generalized Curvatures of the whole {Surface}.
- 1.21) **Statement 1.4.** To a {Bare Manifold w.b.} the Maker adjoined a {Structure}, so that in the ensuing {param. Manif. w.b.} the Maps be bijective.
- 1.22) **Identification.** Identification is a kind of Superposition: it means to form a {Class of equivalent Elements of a {Space 1}} and to assume this {Class} as an Element of a {Space 2}. A cautionary attitude: in this paper *No Identification of this kind, to avoid infringement of Bijective Maps.*
- 1.23) **Curves.** Any {Curve} shall be considered an infinite set of points.
- 1.23.1) A {Curve} is periodic if its points can be retraced.

1.23.2) **Orders for a Curve.** A Curve can assume a chosen Order as an **ad-joined property**. Orders which may be considered here for a Curve (by the literature) [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [16], [19]:

- a) Linear order (synonyms: serial order, usual order relation) with a dyadic relation and a representation by a set of points on a line with a specified sense;
- b) Betweenness with a ternary relation and a representation by a set of points on a line without distinction of sense;
- c) Cyclic order with a ternary relation and a representation by a set of points on a [Closed Curve] with a specified sense;
- d) Separation (a.k.a. Separation of pairs) with a tetradic relation and a representation by a set of points on a [Loop] without distinction of sense.

1.24) **{Initial & Final Intrinsic Half Ends of an Object}** \subset {Object}. They are within the $\{Intrinsic Observer\}_{Object}$'s {Field of Observation}.

Example: {Initial Intrinsic Half Point}, {Final Intrinsic Half Point} of a {Curve}.

1.25) To avoid *Identification*, we introduce: **{Oriented Point}**.

Say: $\{\rightarrow P\}[P\rightarrow] = \{\rightarrow P\rightarrow\} = \text{Oriented } \{P\}$, shortly $\{P\}$.

{Aft P} = $\{\rightarrow P\}$, {Fore P} = $[P\rightarrow]$ in contact, no {Complement Space} between.

Either on an [**Oriented** Linear Interval] or on an [**Oriented** Closed Curve]:

1.26) In this study, to be simple: {Initial Intrinsic Point}, {Final Intrinsic Point} correspond to No.s in \mathbb{Z} .

1.27) [**Linear Interval**]. Continuous, not self-intersecting, ordered & oriented, closed & bounded [Linear Interval]= I . A Maker-applied Parametrization. In it: {Association:Order&Orientation of {Parameter}, Order&Orientation of {Points}}.

1.27.1) {Intrinsic Boundary} $_I$: {Initial Half Point} = $[0 \rightarrow]$ and {Final Half Point} = $\{\rightarrow F]$. Necessarily distinct, since not adjacent along the [Linear Interval] $_I$. An Intrinsic Distance between them. These "Half Points" are intrinsic, hence the $\{Intrinsic Observer\}_I$ senses: $[[0 \rightarrow], \dots, \{\rightarrow F]$. She cannot sense its {Exterior Half Points}, and its eventual fore and aft continuations.

1.27.2) **Bijective Map.** In Int [Linear Interval] $_I$: an {Oriented Point}= $\{\rightarrow P\}[P\rightarrow]$, shortly $\{P\}$, corresponds to a Parameter Value $u\{P\}$. In {Intr. Boundary} $_I$: $[0\rightarrow]$ corresponds to Parameter Value $u\{0\}$, $\{\rightarrow F]$ to Parameter Value $u\{F\}$.

1.28) [**Closed Curve**]. (According to the literature, a [Closed Curve] is a regular curve of the form $y = [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, such that $y(a) = y(b)$ and all derivatives match: $y'(a) = y'(b)$, $y''(a) = y''(b), \dots$).

Here, a [Closed Curve], supposedly parametrized by the Maker, is defined: regular, ordered, oriented; closed by {Positional Continuity} and by a specified {Frenet frame Continuity} \approx {Parametric Continuity}. With two Intrinsic Distances: 1] one non-null $[\{Initial Half Point\} \leftrightarrow \text{Int Curve} \leftrightarrow \{Final Half Point\}]$; 2] one null $[\{Final Half Point\} \xrightarrow{\text{contact}} \{Initial Half Point\}]$.

1.28.1) Say: {Initial Half Point}, {Final Half Point} constitute the {Oriented Point} = $\{\rightarrow N \rightarrow\}$, shortly $\{N\}$, that is dubbed by the No. $\{N\}$: *no Identification*. $\{N\}$ may be any Number on the parametrized [Closed Curve], but it is chosen as a Initial/Final Reference. If one wish to be simple: $\{N\} \in \mathbb{Z}$.

1.28.2) Hence a [Closed Curve] is a *special Interval*, which starts from and returns to *the same* {Oriented Point} = $\{\rightarrow N\}[N \rightarrow]$. $[N \rightarrow]$, $\{\rightarrow N]$

make a singleton, but they are distinguishable in the Oriented [Closed Curve].

1.28.3) By said Continuity: smooth {Transitions: $[N \rightarrow] \leftrightarrow \{ \rightarrow N \}$ }.

1.29) **Ordered & oriented superposed in contact {Closed Curves}**.

Let the Curves have the same Directions & Orientations, and be distinguishable by the Parametrization. A Specifier for a [Closed Curve] $_J \subset \{\text{Closed Curves}\}$: the {Number}= $\{J\}$; $0 \leq \{J\} \leq J_{Max}$; $\{J\} \in \mathbb{Z}$, belongs to said [Closed Curve] $_J$, to its {Initial/Final Point} = $\{ \rightarrow J \rightarrow \}$, it is the Integer of the {No.s} of the Points of the Int [Closed Curve] $_J$. The {Initial/Final Point} = $\{J\}$ of the [Closed Curve] $_J$ shows that it is a [Closed Curve], not a Spiral.

{ [$[0 \rightarrow] \dots 0.1 \dots 0.9 \dots \{ \rightarrow 0 \}$] , [$[1 \rightarrow] \dots 1.1 \dots 1.9 \dots \{ \rightarrow 1 \}$] , ... } .

1.29.1) {Positional Continuity}: no interposition of {Complement Space} within any [Closed Curve] and within the {Closed Curves}. The {Positional Continuity} means that the {Closed Curves} is a {Geometrical Object}.

1.29.2) The {Powerful Intrinsic Observer} $_{\{\text{Closed Curves}\}}$ on her [Residence Closed Curve] senses the entire {Closed Curves} and non-smooth {Transitions from one [Closed Curve] to another } ,

1.30) **{Extrinsic Observer}'s analysis of a Surface**. Let an {Extrinsic Observer} know a parametrized, differentiable Surface $\mathbb{X}(u, v)$ in $\{\mathbb{R}^2\}$, with basis $\{\sigma_u, \sigma_v\}$ and Gauss Map $\nu : \mathbb{X}(u, v) \rightarrow \mathbb{X}(x, y, z)$ in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$, that gives $\mathbb{X}(u, v, f(u, v))$ in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ with basis $\{\sigma_u, \sigma_v, \nu\}$ (Not an orthonormal basis).

1.31) **I1 ✘ A Surface's Orientation: {Circular Arrow field}**.

A Surface X can have a {Circ. Arrow field} $_X$ in its {Structure} $_X$. [21].

1.31.1) **Locally in {n.b.h.} = $\sigma = \Delta\mathbb{X}$** . As σ -intrinsic definers of {Circ. Arrow} $_\sigma$, at a Point $P(u, v)$ of a chosen {n.b.h.} = $\sigma(u, v)$, (let us say: the Initial Patch), the Maker assumes the vectors σ_u, σ_v and one of the possible {Circ. Arrows}: $\{\sigma_u \text{ then } \sigma_v\}$ or $\{\sigma_v \text{ then } \sigma_u\}$. In $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ they are represented by: $[\sigma_u \times \sigma_v] / \|\sigma_u \times \sigma_v\|$, $[\sigma_v \times \sigma_u] / \|\sigma_v \times \sigma_u\|$.

1.31.2) **Globally in \mathbb{X}** . If said Maker-chosen {Circ. Arrow} $_\sigma$ smoothly extends to the entire \mathbb{X} , that means an assumed Maker-chosen smooth {Circ. Arrow field} $_{\mathbb{X}}$ for \mathbb{X} . If it is drawn on \mathbb{X} , then it becomes an element of {Structure} $_{\mathbb{X}}$.

1.32) Associated to \mathbb{X} and to a chosen Curve $c(s)$ on \mathbb{X} : the orthonormal {Darboux frame} = $\{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{u}, \nu\}$. Tangent to \mathbb{X} $\{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{t}\}$, $\mathbf{u} \perp \mathbf{t}$. ν is not defined by κ but by $\mathbf{t} \times \mathbf{u} = \nu$. $\kappa \mathbf{n} = \kappa_n \nu + \kappa_g \mathbf{u}$. $\kappa^2 = \kappa_g^2 + \kappa_n^2$.

By a Darboux frame, no locally undefined (U.N.V.) due to an eventual $\kappa = 0$.

1.33) **At the {Initial Patch} = $\Delta\mathbb{X}_0$** . The $(\nu)_{\Delta\mathbb{X}_0}$ that the Maker associates to the {Circ. Arrow} $_{\Delta\mathbb{X}_0}$ and the $(\nu)_{\Delta\mathbb{X}_0}$ that he assumes in the {Darboux trihedral} $_{\Delta\mathbb{X}_0}$ pertain to the same $\Delta\mathbb{X}_0$ and have the same Direction $\perp \Delta\mathbb{X}_0$. Obviously the Maker assumes the same Orientation for them: an unique $(\nu)_{\Delta\mathbb{X}_0}$.

1.34) **{Powerful Intrinsic Observer} $_{\mathcal{X}}$'s Orientation assessing**. Let \mathcal{X} have {Structure} $_{\mathcal{X}}$ including its {Circ. Arrow vector field} $_{\mathcal{X}}$ and corresponding $\{\nu\}_{\mathcal{X}}$. Then each {n.b.h.} = $\Delta\mathcal{X}_u$ has its {Circ. Arrow vector} $_{\Delta\mathcal{X}_u}$, either undefined i.e. assumed scalar value 0, or a non-null scalar value, either 1 or -1. The {Powerful Intrinsic Observer} $_{\mathcal{X}}$ moves within her {Residence Side} $_{\mathcal{X}}$, not out of it. She has her own specified {Circ. Arrow vector} $_{\{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}_{\mathcal{X}}}$, not necessarily equal to her local {Circ. Arrow vector} $_{\Delta\mathcal{X}_u}$. She uses her

{Circ. Arrow vector} as reference in her analysis of \mathcal{X} . A (*Powerful Intrinsic Observer* u_t) \mathcal{X} 's {Local Comparison: {Circ. Arrow vector} $_{\Delta\mathcal{X}_u}$, {Circ. Arr. vector} $_{(Pow. Intr. Observer\ u_t)\mathcal{X} @ \Delta\mathcal{X}_u}$ } is an orientation-assessing operation.

1.34.1) **Facilitating, initial assumption at $\Delta\mathcal{X}_0$** , for evaluations in \mathcal{X} :

{Circ. Arrow} $_{(Pow. Intr. Obs.\ \Delta\mathcal{X}_{00})\mathcal{X}} = \{\text{Circ. Arrow}\}_{\Delta\mathcal{X}_0}$.

1.35) **{Intrinsic Observer}'s analysis of a Surface**. Let an imbedded in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ 2-dim Theorist {*Intrinsic Observer*} $_X$ analyze the Surface $X(u, v)$ in $\{\mathbb{R}^2\}$, with {Initial Patch} = $\sigma(u, v)$, that is spanned by the tangent vectors $\{\sigma_u, \sigma_v\}$.

1.35.1) Supposingly, she has a {Gen. Curvatures' Sensor}. For example, a Monitoring device of a drawn on her {Polygon}: Area A and {Boundary} that is a smooth piecewise Curve $c(s)$ with Geodesic Curvature $\kappa_g(s)$. Any state (*Intrinsic Observer* u_t) $_X @ \sigma$, measuring: {Polygon}'s Area, $\kappa_g(s)$, Discontinuity Angles at the Vertices of the {Boundary} and calculating, gets her own Gaussian Curvature K_{InO} . By the {Adhesion: σ , (*Intrinsic Observer* u_t) $_X @ \sigma$ }: $K_{InO} = K_\sigma$.

1.36) **An extension in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$** . The Theorist {*Intrinsic Observer*} $_X$, having the concepts of Spaces, Dimensions, Directions, Cross product conceives:

Non-null {Normal Direction} $_{\{Intrinsic\ Observer\}_X @ \sigma} = \{\text{Normal Direction}\}_\sigma$. (Orientation not yet considered).

1.36.1) Having also the concept of Orientation, the Theorist {*Intrinsic Observer*} $_X$ senses two possible, different Orientations for the specified {Normal Direction} $_\sigma$. Two different Orientations mean two distinct Surfaces. One has the Maker-imposed, and {*Intrinsic Observer*} $_X @ \sigma$ - directly sensed {Circ. Arrow} $_\sigma$ with its corresponding (U.N.V.) $_\sigma$. The other, with opposite {Circ. Arrow} and opposite (U.N.V.), is only conceived by the Theorist {*Intrinsic Observer*} $_X @ \sigma$. It is said "conceived" because the {*Intrinsic Observer*} $_X$'s Field of Observation is, by definition, limited to one Surface.

1.36.2) {*Intrinsic Observer*} $_X @ \sigma$ understands that {Circ. Arrow} $_\sigma$ was got by elements of σ only. Newertheless she conceives an Extension: the Representation of said {Circ. Arrow} $_\sigma \in \sigma$ by a (Unit Normal Vector) $_\sigma = (\nu)_\sigma \in \{\mathbb{R}^3\}$.

1.36.3) **Globally**. {*Intrinsic Observer*} $_X$ senses the {Circ. Arrow vector field} $_X$ and does not directly sense, but conceives the {U.N.V. field} $_X = \{\nu\}_X$.

1.36.4) **Locally** the {*Intrinsic Observer*} $_X$ attains the idea of associating the measured scalar value K_σ to the directed and oriented unit vector ν_σ .

1.37) Also the {*Intrinsic Observer*} $_X$ can attain the idea of the Gauss map $\nu : X(u, v) \rightarrow X(u, v, \nu) \in \{\mathbb{R}^3\}$, meaning: $X(u, v)$ is imbedded in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$.

1.38) **Locally**. By scalar products of the 1st order derivatives, the Theorist {*Intrinsic Observer*} $_\sigma$ gets the 1st Fundamental form. of any σ

1.39) **Locally**. Calculating the 1st and 2nd derivatives on any σ , by 6 equations the Theorist {*Intrinsic Observer*} $_\sigma$ gets its No. 6 {**Christoffel symbols**} $_\sigma$.

1.40) **Locally**. By (U.N.V.) and the 2nd derivatives she gets the coefficients of the 2nd Fundamental form of any σ .

1.41) **Locally**. By the 1st and 2nd Fundamental Forms, she calculates the Gaussian curvature K_σ , the Mean curvature H_σ ; by them the Principal curvatures.

1.42) **A Surface's generic Curve $c(s)$ according to an {Extr. Observer}**.

1.42.1) By ν , the {*Extrinsic Observer*} maps $c(s) \subset X(u, v)$ into $c(s) \subset X(x, y, z)$.

- 1.42.2) The *{ Extrinsic Observer }* considers the case of an Arc Length Parametrized Curve $c(s)$ in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$, with a Moving Frame of Orthogonal Unit Vectors $\{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{b}\}$.
- a) "Arc Length Parametrization" means: $\|\mathbf{t}\| = \|c'(s)\| = 1$; $\mathbf{t} = c'(s) / \|c'(s)\|$.
- b) $\kappa \mathbf{n} = c''(s)$. The Curvature κ be chosen $\kappa = \|c''(s)\|$; unit $\mathbf{n} = c''(s) / \|c''(s)\|$.
- c) By the above: $c'(s) \cdot c''(s) = 0$; hence $c''(s) = 0 \vee c''(s) \perp c'(s)$.
- d) Chosen Torsion τ so that \mathbf{b} be unit: $\mathbf{b} \tau = \mathbf{n}' + \kappa \mathbf{t}$. $\tau = -\langle c' \times c'', c''' \rangle / [c'']^2$.
- 1.42.3) (If the *{ Extrinsic Observer }* considers the general case, he discards arc length - parametrized Curve's formulae). [26], [13]
- 1.43) **Geodesic curve = $c(s)$ according to an *{ Extrinsic Observer }*.**
- 1.43.1) For a Geodesic: $u'' = F_1(u, v, u', v')$, $v'' = F_2(u, v, u', v')$.
- 1.43.2) For a Geodesic $c(s)$: $\kappa_g = 0$; $c'' \equiv \kappa \mathbf{n} = \kappa_n \mathbf{n} = \kappa_n \nu$; $\tau = \tau_g$; $\mathbf{n} = \nu$ of the Surface; $\mathbf{b} = -\mathbf{u}$; Frenet frame = $\{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{b}\} = \{\mathbf{t}, \nu, -\mathbf{u}\}$; $\mathbf{n}' = -\kappa_n \mathbf{t} + \tau_g \mathbf{b}$.
- 1.44) **A Surface's Curve according to a Theorist *{ Intrinsic Observer }*_X.**
- 1.44.1) Supposedly a non-parametrized curve Shape be considered on X by the Theorist *{ Intrinsic Observer }*_X. Choosing a set of Control Points on X , she approximates the Shape with a parametrized Curve $c(s)$; supposedly no Splines.
- 1.44.2) Being a Theorist and knowing the algorithms, she calculates the **vector 1st derivative** $c'(s) = \mathbf{t}$ for suitable values $\{s\}$ of $c(s)$ in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$.
- 1.44.3) She gets for points of $c(s) \in \{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ the **Curvature vector derivative** $c''(s)$ and assumes: $c''(s) \equiv \kappa \mathbf{n}$.
 $\|c''(s)\| = \kappa$. $\{\text{Unit Normal Vector field}\} = \{\mathbf{n}\} = c''(s) / \|c''(s)\|$.
- 1.44.4) She gets by derivatives the unit $[c'(s) \times c''(s)] / \|c'(s) \times c''(s)\| = \mathbf{b}$.
- 1.44.5) For points of $c(s) \in \{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ she calculates the Vector derivative $c'''(s)$.
- 1.44.6) For said points and by derivatives she calculates: $\tau = -[c' c'' c'''] / [c'']^2$.
- 1.44.7) For each value (s) of $c(s)$ she conceives a (U. Tangent V.) = $\mathbf{u} \perp \mathbf{t}$ on X .
- 1.44.8) At (s) of $c(s)$: (Unit Normal Vector) = $(\nu) = (\mathbf{t}) \times (\mathbf{u})$; $(\nu) \perp X$. $(\nu) \in \{\nu\}$.
- 1.44.9) The Theorist *{ Intrinsic Observer }*_X gets in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ the orthonormal **Frenet-Serret frame** = $\{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{b}\}$. By κ , τ , \mathbf{n} she gets $\mathbf{t}' = \kappa \mathbf{n}$, $\mathbf{b}' = -\tau \mathbf{n}$.
- 1.44.10) Within the set of Curves on X and calculating derivatives, the Theorist *{ Intrinsic Observer }*_X finds a **Geodesic**; she knows $\{\mathbf{n}\} = \{\nu\}$ for it.
- 1.45) **Smoothness.** The *{ Smooth Structure }* of a Manifold has many possible formulations. [14] [18] [21] [13]
- 1.45.1) $I \ 2 \ \nabla$. It is worth mentioning that a single *{ Chart }* covering an entire *{ Manifold }* implies a *{ Smooth Structure }* of this *{ Manifold }*.
- 1.45.2) Also, that a *{ Smooth Structure }* implies a *{ Smooth Manifold }*. [14]
- 1.45.3) A *{ Smooth, charted Structure }* must be specified:
 C^k differentiable, $0 \leq k \leq \infty$.
- 1.45.4) In this paper, it is assumed that Smoothness of an entire Manifold is judged checking a set $\{\text{Transitions: } \{\text{n.b.h.}\}_h \leftrightarrow \{\text{n.b.h.}\}_k\}$; $\forall h, k$.
- 1.45.5) A Manifold's *{ Parametric Continuity }* in the $\{\text{Transitions: } \{\text{n.b.h.}\}_h \leftrightarrow \{\text{n.b.h.}\}_k\}$ is evaluated by calculus.
- 1.46) **Parametric Continuity of a Surface.**
- 1.46.1) The *{ Parametric Continuity }* is associated to the set of partial derivatives.
- 1.46.2) "Order of Continuity" = "No. of matching derivatives".

2 {param. 2-Manif. w. b.} , {Observation Implement}.

2.1) Dealing with the *{Möbius strip}*, the literature introduces an observable Mobile Shape. This Shape is here dubbed *{Observation Implement}*.

2.1.1) An *{Observation Implement}* is not a part of the {param. 2-Manif. w.b.}. It is an introduced mobile reference part of $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$, moving independently from the {Bimodal Intrinsic Observer}. It may be in contact and wander the {param. 2-Manif. w. b.}. Its set of emitted Signals allow its detection.

2.1.2) The *{Observation Implement}* is directly observed by the $\{\{Intrinsic Observer\}, \{Powerful Intrinsic Observer\}\}$ when it is in her field of observation.

2.2) **Vector {Observation Implement}: {OIV}**. Aft point A, midpoint O, front point F; no top, no bottom, no left, no right, no {Circular Arrow}.

2.3) **A 2-dim {Observation Implement}: {OBIM}**. Fig.1. A flexible oriented quadric, always adhering the {param. 2-Manif. w.b.}: midpoint O, left L, front F, right R, aft A; one Maker-chosen {Circular Arrow}. Globally, an $\{\{Intrinsic Observer\}, \{Powerful Intrinsic Observer\}\}$ senses {OBIM} as a set of Aspects: {Recto OBIM, Verso OBIM, Null OBIM}, corresponding to a set {Relative Positions: $\{\{Intrinsic Observer\}, \{Powerful Intrinsic Observer\}\}$, {OBIM}}. Locally, an (*Intrinsic Observer*_{u t}) senses one of said Aspects of {OBIM}.

3 {param.2-Manif.w.b.}, {Signal System}, {Observer}.

3.1) Distinct {Observers} analyze different {Objects}, since they have different {perceiving capabilities} and {modalities of analysis}.

3.2) In this study: to each *specified* {Manifold}, its own *specified* {Observer}.

3.3) Avoiding noise, simplifying the analysis and its report. In the {Complement Space}, only *{Intrinsic Observer}*, *{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}*, *{Observation Implement}*, *Instruments* emit Signals: not to be assumed {Manifold} Signals.

3.4) The analysis of a {param. 2-Manif. w.b.} implies a Name for it, say: \mathbb{X} , X , \mathcal{X} , ...; a Name for its {Observer}, say: $\{Extrinsic Observer\}_{\mathbb{X}}$, Simple $\{Intrinsic Observer\}_X$, Theorist $\{Intrinsic Observer\}_X$, $\{Powerful Intrinsic Observer\}_{\mathcal{X}}$, ...

3.5) **Analysis in Time.** 3.5.1) In a Time instant: (*Intrinsic Observer*_{u t}) state's Observation and Memorization. 3.5.2) In a discrete Time interval: *{Intrinsic Observer}*'s ordered set of Observations and Memorizations.

3.6) **{Analysis Space}**_X = {Manifold X, {Signal System}_X, *{Observation Implement}*_X, {Instruments}, *{Intrinsic Observer}*_X}.

3.6.1) Locally. In one (*Analysis Space*_{u i t})_X state, (which by definition of "state" has its elements in specified relative spatial positions). Its (*Intrinsic Observer*_{u i t})_X @ ΔX_{u_i} state, where ΔX_{u_i} is her {Reception n.b.h.}, has within her an {Image}, i.e. the {Sensation} of the {Reception n.b.h.} = $\Delta X_{u_i} \in X$.

3.6.2) Globally, the set {Images of X}_{Intrinsic Observer}_X corresponds to the set {Aspects}_X = $\{\Delta X_{u_i}; \forall u_i\} = X$, i.e. X according to *{Intrinsic Observer}*_X.

3.6.3) Similarly for {Analysis Space}_X.

3.6.4) Locally. In one (*Analysis Space*_{u i t})_X state, a (*Powerful Intrinsic Observer*_{u i t})_X @ $\Delta \mathcal{X}_{u_i}$, where $\Delta \mathcal{X}_{u_i}$ is her {Reception n.b.h.}, has within her

the (Powerful Intrinsic Observer $u_i t$)'s {Image}, i.e. the {Sensation} of the {Perception N.B.H.} = $\{ \Delta \mathcal{X}_{u_i} \} \in \mathcal{X}$.

3.6.5) Globally, the set {Images of \mathcal{X} } $\{ \text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer} \}_{\mathcal{X}}$ corresponds to the set {Aspects} $\mathcal{X} = \{ \{ \Delta \mathcal{X}_{u_i} \}; \forall u_i \} = \mathcal{X}$.

3.7) **Signals.** 3.7.1) An assumption, to simplify the analysis and its report, avoiding noise. Exclusion of {Complement Space}-emitted Signals and {Complement Space} - crossing Signals.

3.7.2) **{Associates' Signals}**. The {Associates}-emitted Signals do not pertain to the set {Manifold's Signals}. The Analyzer receives them and uses their information.

3.7.3) **{Manifold's Signals}**. a) Manif.-emitted, then Manif.-received Signals; b) Manif.-emitted, {Complement Space}-crossing, then Manif.-received Signals.

3.7.4) **{Intrinsic Signals}** $_X = \{ X \text{-emitted, } X \text{-carried, } X \text{-received Signals} \}$.

3.7.5) **{Intrinsic Signals}** $_{\mathcal{X}} = \{ \mathcal{X} \text{-emitted, } \mathcal{X} \text{-carried, } \mathcal{X} \text{-received Signals} \}$.

3.7.6) **{Powerful Intrinsic Signals}** $_{\mathcal{X}} \subset \{ \text{Intrinsic Signals} \}_{\mathcal{X}}$. They can effect also non-smooth Transitions within \mathcal{X} . Examples. a) Patch A \leftrightarrow adjacent Patch B. b) Patch C \leftrightarrow superposed Patch Verso D. c) Patch E \leftrightarrow adjacent Patch Verso F.

3.8) **III 1 ✖ For X & \mathcal{X} : {Intrinsic Bimodal Observer} =**
 $\{ \{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X, \{ \text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer} \}_{\mathcal{X}} \}$.

3.8.1) {Field of Observation} $\{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \} \neq$

{Field of Observation} $\{ \text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer} \}$.

3.8.2) The $\{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X$, sensing X by the {Signal System} $_X$, performs a “ X -intrinsic analysis”. The $\{ \text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer} \}_{\mathcal{X}}$, sensing \mathcal{X} by the {Signal System} $_{\mathcal{X}}$, performs an “ \mathcal{X} -intrinsic analysis”.

3.8.3) **Statement 3.1.** The $\{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X$ uses only information regarding intrinsic properties of X to get an *abstract definition* of X .

The $\{ \text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer} \}_{\mathcal{X}}$ uses only informations regarding intrinsic properties of \mathcal{X} to get an *abstract definition* of \mathcal{X} .

3.8.4) The $\{ \text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer} \}_{\mathcal{X}}$ has the ability of sensing Superposed n.b.h.s, and adjacent n.b.h.s, to any {Reception n.b.h.} of \mathcal{X} .

3.8.5) **{Intrinsic Bimodal Observer}'s properties.** a) **Direct Senses:** Sight, Taste, Touch, ... b) **Indirect Senses:** Memory, Intelligence, Time senses, ..., Instruments and measuring procedures. c) Use of an $\{ \text{Observation Implement} \}$. d) Concepts' formulations. e) Logic, Math. f) A **Generalized Curvatures' Sensor** within her Senses. g) If a Theorist, the Gauss Curvature's concept.

III 2 ✖ h) Adhesion & Flexibility. The $\{ \{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X, \{ \text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer} \}_{\mathcal{X}} \}$ moves in her Surface remaining adherent to it. She is a 2-dim-object $\subset \{ \mathbb{R}^3 \}$ that is flexible in $\{ \mathbb{R}^3 \}$. (A rigid {Bimodal Observer} cannot be intrinsic to a generally non-planar Surface). She changes her Curvatures in $\{ \mathbb{R}^3 \}$ (a limited adaptation: Curvatures $\ll \infty$). She is an Organism; by her senses she assesses and measures her own changes in $\{ \mathbb{R}^3 \}$. An ($\text{Intrinsic Observer}_{u_t}$) $_X$ by her adhesion to X , or a ($\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}_{u_t}$) $_{\mathcal{X}}$ by her adhesion to \mathcal{X} , deduces that her sensed Gen. Curvatures equal the Gen. Curvatures of respectively her {Reception n.b.h.} $_X$, {Reception n.b.h.} $_{\mathcal{X}}$.

- 3.8.6) $\{ \{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X, \{ \text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer} \}_X \}$ has her own, fixed to her, $\{ \text{Reference Frame} \} \{ \{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X, \{ \text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer} \}_X \}$.
- 3.8.7) $\{ \{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X, \{ \text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer} \}_X \}$ observes and can distinguish Submanifolds: of X, \mathcal{X} respectively.
- 3.9) **Statement 3.2.** The $\{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X$'s attribute: "Intrinsic to X " implies: a) she is not an element of X . b) She deems herself an inhabitant of X .
- 3.9.1) Similarly for $\{ \text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer} \}_X, \mathcal{X}$.
- 3.10) **Smooth X .** According to the $\{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X$, X is smooth if all its global intrinsic properties appear smooth.
- 3.10.1) Similarly for \mathcal{X} , according to the $\{ \text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer} \}_X$.
- 3.11) **Modality: $\{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X$.**
- 3.11.1) **The $\{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X$'s analysis of X .** This analysis must be organized rationally. The following organized analysis is a possible choice.
- 3.11.2) **$\{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X$'s Field of Movements** is the 1st concern.
- 3.11.3) **$\{ \text{Correlation I: } X, \{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X \}$.**
The $\{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X$ is always in contact with X . *Not leaving, not rotating out of X , not peeping out of the Boundary, using an Instrument for its detection.* Going out and reentering: her "intrinsic to X " attribute must be considered lost, since the gain of extrinsic information is not excluded.
- 3.11.4) **$\{ \text{Initial Correlation II: } \Delta X_0, (\text{Intrinsic Observer}_{00})_X \text{ state} \}$.**
The $(\text{Intrinsic Observer}_{00})_X$ initial state must have directions, orientations, $\{ \text{Circ. Arrow} \}$, Gen. Curvatures, equal to those of $\Delta X_0 = \{ \text{Initial n.b.h. of } X \}$.
- 3.11.5) Smooth continuation: **$\{ \text{Correlation II: } X, \{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X \}$.**
Any $(\text{Intrinsic Observer}_{ut})_X$ has directions, orientations, $\{ \text{Circ. Arrow} \}$, Gen. Curvatures, equal to those of her $\{ \text{Reception n.b.h.} \} = \Delta X_u; \forall \Delta X_u$.
- 3.11.6) **$\{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X$'s relative to X Principal Motion:** sliding along $[\text{Midline}]_X$. **$\{ \text{Secondary analyzing Motions in } X \}$** are allowed.
- 3.11.7) An $\{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X$ receives, and considers pertaining to X , the Signals from X . She cannot sense: a) more than one Sheet of X ; b) Signals from outside her $\{ \text{Reception n.b.h.} \}$; c) Signals from outside the $\{ \text{Intrinsic Boundary's Half Edges towards Int } X \}_X$. Moreover:
- 3.11.8) An $\{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X$ receives and elaborates Signals from Herself, Instruments, $\{ \text{OBIM} \}_X$: they are "Associates to X ", but not "Elements of X ".
- 3.11.9) Any $(\text{Intrinsic Observer}_{ut})_X$ state adheres to her $\{ \text{Reception n.b.h.} \}$ that has \approx her size, assuming the same Gen. Curvatures. For example, in a $\{ \text{Ruled Surface} \}$, the $\{ \text{Reception n.b.h.} \} = \{ \Delta u_i \times [\mathbf{V}_{u_i}] \}$. Little Δu_i , but allowing the perception of the Gen. Curvatures and $\{ \text{Circ. Arrow} \}$ of the $\{ \text{Reception n.b.h.} \}$.
- 3.11.10) The $\{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X$ does not sense outside X , hence not the **Self-Contacts of X** outside the $\{ \text{Boundary Half Edges towards Int } X \}$.
- 3.11.11) One may say: the $\{ \text{Intrinsic Observer} \}_X$ is near-sighted, narrow-aimed, sensible to a limited $\{ \text{Signal System} \}_X$, but not overburdened with X -extrinsic, unnecessary information.
- 3.12) **Modality $\{ \text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer} \}_X$.**
- 3.12.1) Similarly, $\{ \text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer} \}_X$ moves in \mathcal{X} referring to \mathcal{X} .

3.12.2) **Statement 3.3.** In the case of a many-sided \mathcal{X} . The $\{Powerful\ Intrinsic\ Observer\}_{\mathcal{X}}$ cannot be in all $\{Sides\}_{\mathcal{X}}$: she cannot leave the Side in which she is, dubbed the $\{Residence\ Side\}_{\mathcal{X}}$, to enter into another Side.

3.12.3) Locally, she is in sensory contact with n.b.h.s of all the $\{Sheets\}_{\mathcal{X}}$.

3.12.4) She can decompose mentally a many-sheeted \mathcal{X} into a set $\{Sheets\}_{\mathcal{X}}$, envisaging a foliated $\{Structure\}_{\mathcal{X}}$. And into Sides a many-sided \mathcal{X} .

3.12.5) She perceives the Self-Contacts of \mathcal{X} as pertaining to a larger Space.

3.13) **The class of Observers**, according to the $\{Extrinsic\ Observer\}$.

3.13.1) $\{\mathbf{Bimodal\ Intrinsic\ Observer}\} = \{\{\mathbf{AF}\}, \{\mathbf{pAF}\}\}$. It is a small (in comparison with the Manifold), *flexible curve* of non-null length, always adhering to the Manifold. With Ends A, F; $A \neq F$; chosen linear Orientation $\{A \rightarrow F\}$. Without the properties Left/Right, Down/Up, $\{Circ.\ Arrow\}$.

The modality $\{\mathbf{AF}\}$ perceives $\{Intrinsic\ Signals\}$. The modality $\{\mathbf{pAF}\}$ perceives $\{Intrinsic\ Signals\} \supset \{Powerful\ Intrinsic\ Signals\}$.

3.13.2) $\{\mathbf{Bimodal\ Intrinsic\ Observer}\} = \{\{\mathbf{LFRA}\}, \{\mathbf{pLFRA}\}\}$.

Modality of Observation: $\{Intrinsic\ Observer\} = \{\mathbf{LFRA}\}$.

Modality of Observation: $\{Powerful\ Intrinsic\ Observer\} = \{\mathbf{pLFRA}\}$.

It is a small flexible quadric, always adhering to her $\{param.\ 2-Manif.\ w.b.\}$.

With a Structure, i.e. adjoined intrinsic properties: an Orientation; four Edges, having Midpoints L, F, R, A; a Maker-chosen, and marked, $\{Circ.\ Arrow\}$, e.g. $\{L \rightarrow F \rightarrow R \rightarrow A\}$.

If the $\{\{\mathbf{LFRA}\}, \{\mathbf{pLFRA}\}\}$ is a theorist, she conceives also, without directly sensing it, the correspondingly directed, and with a chosen Orientation, Vector $[\nu]$,

1.13.2.1) By definition, any $\{\mathbf{LFRA}\}$'s $\{Reception\ n.b.h.\}$, say $(\mathbf{LFRA}_{ut}) @ \Delta X_u$, is never associated to $\{Superposed\ n.b.h.s\}$.

1.13.2.2) Any $\{\mathbf{pLFRA}\}$'s $\{Reception\ n.b.h.\}$, say $(\mathbf{pLFRA}_{ut}) @ \Delta \mathcal{X}_u$, may be associated to $\{Superposed\ n.b.h.s\}$. She is never associated to:

superposed herself $(\mathbf{pLFRA}_{u_s t'}) @ \Delta \mathcal{X}_{u_s} \vee Verso (\mathbf{pLFRA}_{u_s t'}) @ Verso \Delta \mathcal{X}_{u_s}$. Hence $\{\mathbf{pLFRA}\}$ directly senses a *one-sheeted one-sided herself*.

(A Theorist $\{\mathbf{pLFRA}\}$ can mentally conceive two Aspects of herself, but that is not an argument of this paper).

3.13.3) $\{\mathbf{LFRADU}\}$, a spatially 3-dimensional $\{Intrinsic\ Observer\}$, cannot be intrinsic to a Surface.

3.13.4) $\{\mathbf{Extrinsic\ Observer}\}$. The $\{Extrinsic\ Observer\}$ operates in $\{\mathbb{R}^{3+1}\}$, also as the $\{Intrinsic\ Observers\}$'s $\{Observer\}$.

4 $\{param.\ 2-Manifold\ w.\ b.\}$, $\{Signal\ System\}$, $\{Observation\ Implement\}$, $\{\mathbf{Bimodal\ Intrinsic\ Observer}\}$

4.1) In an $\{\mathbf{Analysis\ Space}\}_X = \{\{Ambient\ Space\}=X, \{Intrinsic\ Observer\}_X, \{Observation\ Implement\}_X, Instruments, \{Signal\ System\}_X\}$.

4.2) **Statement 4.1.** The $\{Intrinsic\ Observer\}_X$, the $\{Observation\ Implement\}_X$: a) are not elements of the $\{Bare\ Manif.\ w.b.\}$. b) Being mobile references, they are not elements of an adjoined $\{Structure\}_X$. Hence they are not elements of X .

- 4.3) The Relations among the Elements of the $\{\text{Analysis Space}\}_X$ are *intrinsic properties* of the $\{\text{Analysis Space}\}_X$, not of X .
- 4.4) Let a “clean analysis” be that performed without sensible modifications of X due to $\{\text{Intrinsic Observer}\}_X$, $\{\text{Observation Implement}\}_X$, Instruments, $\{\text{Signal System}\}_X$; i.e. not adding marks, symbols, etc. to the Maker-given $\{\text{Structure}\}_X$.
- 4.5) The “Analysis” regards $\{\text{Bare } X\} \cup \text{Maker-adjointed } \{\text{Structure}\}_X$.
- 4.5.1) Necessarily the X ” is that described at the analysis’s end.
- 4.6) By the Interactions of the Elements of the $\{\text{Analysis Space}\}_X$, the $\{\text{Intrinsic Observer}\}_X$ builds her *absolute definition* of X .
- 4.7) In an $\{\text{Analysis Space}\}_X = \{\{\text{Ambient Space}\} = \mathcal{X}, \{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}_X, \{\text{Observation Implement}\}_X, \text{Instruments}, \{\text{Signal System}\}_X\}$: considerations similar to those for the $\{\text{Analysis Space}\}_X$.
- 4.7.1) The $\{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}_X$ can perceive the $\{\text{Aspects}\}$: Recto $\{\text{Observation Implement}\}_X$, Verso $\{\text{Observation Implement}\}_X$.
- 4.7.2) The Relations among the Elements of the $\{\text{Analysis Space}\}_X$ are *intrinsic properties* of the $\{\text{Analysis Space}\}_X$, not of \mathcal{X} .
- 4.7.3) By the interactions of the Elements of the $\{\text{Analysis Space}\}_X$, the $\{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}_X$ builds her *absolute definition* of \mathcal{X} .

5 Strips: $\{\mathbb{S}\}, \{\mathcal{S}\}$.

- 5.1) $\{\mathbb{S}\}$.The Maker in \mathbb{R}^{3+1} got $\{\mathbb{S}\}$ applying $\{\text{Structure}\}_{\{\mathbb{S}\}} \supset$ a single, entirely covering $\{\text{Chart}\}_{\{\mathbb{S}\}}$ to a $\{\text{Bare Strip}\} = \{\mathcal{S}\}$. He senses a null-thickness $\{\mathbb{S}\}$. When he does not sense $\{\text{Superposition of Structures, say Charts}\}$, and not sensing by Touch two Sides, he defines $\{\mathbb{S}\}$ one-sheeted one-sided.
- 5.2) $\{\mathcal{S}\}$.The $\{\text{Intrinsic Observer}\}_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$ analyzes and names $\{\mathcal{S}\}$ the Maker’s $\{\mathbb{S}\}$. She does not know thickness. $\{\text{Intrinsic Observer}\}_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$ ’s concept of $\{\mathcal{S}\}$ lays in her set $\{\text{Reception n.b.h.s}\}$: an oriented one-sheeted one-sided $\{\text{param. 2-Manifold w. b.}\}$; with $\{\text{Structure}\}_{\{\mathcal{S}\}} \supset$ a single $\{\text{Chart}\}_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$; Rectangular planform; length (\mathcal{L}) between the intrinsically sensed $\{\text{Oriented Half Endpoints}\}$: $[0 \rightarrow]_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}, \{\rightarrow 1\}_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$ of the geodesic $[\text{Midline}]_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$; width ℓ_0 . Small ℓ_0/\mathcal{L} , to allow the formation of a $\{\text{Möbius strip}\}$ without creases: [27].
- 5.3)Lengthwise Coordinate $[\text{Origin}[0 \rightarrow]; [0 \rightarrow] \leq u \leq \{\rightarrow 1\}]_{\{\mathcal{S}\}} = [u]_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$.
- 5.4) Constant $\{\text{Length of Ruling}\} = \|\mathcal{V}\| = \ell_0$. $[\text{Coordinate along Ruling}] = [v]_{\{\mathcal{S}\}} = [\text{Origin } \{0\}; [-\ell_0/2 \rightarrow] \leq -v/2 \leq \{\rightarrow 0\} [0 \rightarrow] \leq v/2 \leq \{\rightarrow \ell_0/2\}]_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$.
- 5.5) $\{\text{Pairs of Lengthwise Lines, equally oriented by } \{\text{Maker-applied Arrows}\}\} = \{\gamma_{-v/2}, \gamma_{v/2}\}; [-\ell_0/2 \rightarrow] \leq -v/2 \leq \{\rightarrow 0\} [0 \rightarrow] \leq v/2 \leq \{\rightarrow \ell_0/2\}$.
- 5.5.1) $\{\text{Central Pair of Lengthw. Lines}\} = [\text{Midline}]_{\{\mathcal{S}\}} = \{\gamma_{\rightarrow 0}, \gamma_{0\rightarrow}\} = [\gamma_0]_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$.
- 5.5.2) $\{\text{Boundary Pair of Lengthw. Lines}\} = [\gamma_{BT}]_{\{\mathcal{S}\}} = \{\gamma_{B\rightarrow}, \gamma_{\rightarrow T}\}_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$.
- 5.6) Oriented by $[u]_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$, $\{\text{Ruled Surface Vector Field}\}_{\{\mathcal{S}\}} = \{[\mathcal{V}]\}_{\{\mathcal{S}\}} = \{[\mathcal{V}_{[0\rightarrow]}]_{\{\mathcal{S}\}} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow [\mathcal{V}_u]_{\{\mathcal{S}\}} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow [\mathcal{V}_{\{\rightarrow 1\}}]_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}\}$. Its normal to Midline Vectors have equal Widthwise Direction and Orientation. Generic Vector $[\mathcal{V}_u]_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$.
- 5.6.1) Along $[\mathcal{V}_u]_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$: Bottom \rightarrow Midpoint \rightarrow Top i.e. B \rightarrow $\rightarrow 0 \rightarrow$ $\rightarrow T$.
- 5.7)The $\{\text{Intrinsic Observer}\}_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$ senses only the towards Int $\{\mathcal{S}\}$ $\{\text{Half Edges}\}_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$:

- 5.7.1) $\{\text{WidthwiseHalfEdges}\}_{\{S\}}$: $\{[0 \rightarrow] \times \|\mathcal{V}_{[0 \rightarrow]}\|\}_{\{S\}}$, $\{\{\rightarrow 1\} \times \|\mathcal{V}_{\{\rightarrow 1\}}\|\}_{\{S\}}$.
5.7.2) $\{\text{Lengthwise Half Edges}\}_{\{S\}}$: $\{\gamma_{[B \rightarrow]}\}_{\{S\}}$, $\{\gamma_{\{\rightarrow T\}}\}_{\{S\}}$.
5.8) By $\{\text{Induced Orientation}\}$: $[\text{Oriented Intrinsic Boundary}]_{\{S\}} =$
 $[\mathcal{V}_{[0 \rightarrow]}, \gamma_{\{\rightarrow T\}}, -\mathcal{V}_{\{\rightarrow 1\}}, -\gamma_{[B \rightarrow]}]_{\{S\}}$.
5.8.1) A corresponding, Maker-assumed $\{\text{Circular Arrow}\}_{\{S\}}$.

6 Strips: $\{\text{SS}\}$, $\{\text{SS}\}$, $\{\text{DS}\}$, $\{\text{DS}\}$.

- 6.1) $\{\text{SS}\}$. The Maker built $\{\text{SS}\}$ by the precise *Superposition*, and suitable *Orientation*, of two $\mathcal{L} \times \ell_0$ *rectangular structured Strips*: $\{S\}$ and *Verso* $\{S2\}$.
(The construction of $\{\text{CC}\}$ and of $\{\text{MM}\}$, is by $\{\text{SS}\}$).
6.2) $\{\text{SS}\}$ is the $\{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}_{\{\text{SS}\}}$'s perception of the Maker's $\{\text{SS}\}$.
6.3) Any $(\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer } u_t)_{\{\text{SS}\}}$ state in her $\{\text{Residence Side}\} = \{S\}$
has $\{\text{Perception N.B.H.}\} = \{\{\text{Reception n.b.h.}\} \in \{S\}, \{\text{n.b.h.}\} \in \text{Verso } \{S2\}\}$.
6.4) The confined in $\{S\}$ $\{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}_{\{\text{SS}\}}$ senses the *Superposition* of the two *Sheets*: $\{S\}$, *Verso* $\{S2\}$, of $\{\text{SS}\}$. No smooth *Transition* between them: they are its two *Sides*. She perceives:
6.4.1) Same *Dir. & Orient.* of the *Lengthwise Coordinates*: $[u]_{\{S\}}, [u]_{\text{Verso } \{S2\}}$.
6.4.2) Same *Direction & Orientation* by $\{\text{Maker-applied Arrows}\}$, for the entire $\{\text{SS}\}$, of the sensed $[\gamma_{-v/2}]_{\{S\}}, [\gamma_{v/2}]_{\{S\}}, [\gamma_{-v/2}]_{\text{Verso } \{S2\}}, [\gamma_{v/2}]_{\text{Verso } \{S2\}}; \forall v$.
6.4.3) In $\{S\}$. *Opposite* $\{\text{Induced Orientation Arrows}\}$: $[\gamma_{-v/2}]_{\{S\}}, [\gamma_{v/2}]_{\{S\}}; \forall v$.
6.4.4) In *Verso* $\{S2\}$. *Oppos.* $\{\text{Ind.Or.Arr.s}\}$: $[\gamma_{-v/2}]_{\text{Verso } \{S2\}}, [\gamma_{v/2}]_{\text{Verso } \{S2\}}; \forall v$.
6.4.5) *Superposition*, with *opposite* $\{\text{Induced Orientation Arrows}\}$:
 $[\gamma_{-v/2}]_{\{S\}}, [\gamma_{v/2}]_{\text{Verso } \{S2\}}; \forall v$.
6.4.6) *Superposition*, with *opposite* $\{\text{Induced Orientation Arrows}\}$:
 $[\gamma_{v/2}]_{\{S\}}, [\gamma_{-v/2}]_{\text{Verso } \{S2\}}; \forall v$.
6.4.7) *Equal widthwise-direction*, *opposite orientation*: $\{[\mathcal{V}]\}_{\{S\}}, \{[\mathcal{V}]\}_{\text{Verso } \{S2\}}$.
6.4.8) *Equal Widthwise Direction*, *equal Orientation* by $\{\text{Maker-applied Arrows}\}$,
opposite $\{\text{Induced Orientation Arrows}\}$: $[\mathcal{V}_{[0 \rightarrow]}]_{\{S\}}, [\mathcal{V}_{\{\rightarrow 1\}}]_{\{S\}}$.
6.4.9) *Equal Widthwise Direction*, *equal Orientation* by $\{\text{Maker-applied Arrows}\}$,
opposite $\{\text{Induced Orientation Arrows}\}$: $[\mathcal{V}_{[0 \rightarrow]}]_{\text{Verso } \{S2\}}, [\mathcal{V}_{\{\rightarrow 1\}}]_{\text{Verso } \{S2\}}$.
6.4.10) *Superposition*, *equal Widthwise Direction*, *opposite Widthwise Orientation*,
opposite $\{\text{Induced Orientation Arrows}\}$: $[\mathcal{V}_{[0 \rightarrow]}]_{\{S\}}, [\mathcal{V}_{[0 \rightarrow]}]_{\text{Verso } \{S2\}}$.
6.4.11) *Superposition*, *equal Widthwise Direction*, *opposite Widthwise Orientation*,
opposite $\{\text{Induced Orientation Arrows}\}$: $[\mathcal{V}_{\{\rightarrow 1\}}]_{\{S\}}, [\mathcal{V}_{\{\rightarrow 1\}}]_{\text{Verso } \{S2\}}$.
6.4.12) $\{\text{Oriented Intrinsic Boundary}\}_{\{S\}}$, by $\{\text{Induced Orientation Arrows}\}$:
 $[[\mathcal{V}_{[0 \rightarrow]}], [\gamma_{\{\rightarrow T\}}], -[\mathcal{V}_{\{\rightarrow 1\}}], -[\gamma_{[B \rightarrow]}]]_{\{S\}}$.
6.4.13) $\{\text{Oriented Intrinsic Boundary}\}_{\text{Verso } \{S2\}}$, by $\{\text{Ind. Orient. Arrows}\}$:
 $[[\mathcal{V}_{[0 \rightarrow]}], [\gamma_{\{\rightarrow T\}}], -[\mathcal{V}_{\{\rightarrow 1\}}], -[\gamma_{[B \rightarrow]}]]_{\text{Verso } \{S2\}}$.
6.4.14) *Corresponding Maker-assumed* $\{\text{Circ. Arrow}\}_{\{S\}}$. $\{\text{Circ. Arrow}\}_{\text{Verso } \{S2\}}$.
6.4.15) $\{\text{Circ. Arrow}\}_{\text{Verso } \{S2\}} = -\{\text{Circ. Arrow}\}_{\{S\}}$.
6.4.16) *Non-smooth Transitions* of the *Or. Intr. Boundaries*, by the big *Curvature*.
6.5) $\{\text{DS}\}$. The Maker built the two-sheeted/sided **Doubling** $\{\text{DS}\}$, precise *Superposition* of two $\mathcal{L} \times \ell_0$ *rectangular*, *equally structured Strips* $\{S\}$, $\{D\}$. [21]

- 6.6) **{DS}**. The analyzing **{DS}** confined in **{S}** *{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}*_{DS} senses: same directions and orientations for the distinguishable **{Structure}**_{S}, **{Structure}**_{D} of the superposed **{S}**, **{D}** of **{DS}**.
 6.7) **{DS}** may be used for the assembly of **{DC}**, **{DM}**; their analysis is left to the Reader.

7 Cylinders: **{C}**, **{C}**, **{CC}**, **{CC}**.

- 7.1) **{C}**. The Maker got **{C}** bending a Strip **{S}**, placing in Contact without Twist, Superposition, Identification, with a specified Parametric Continuity Order, its **{Initial Widthwise Half Edge}**_{S}, **{Final Widthwise Half Edge}**_{S}, and gluing them together, without interposed **{Complement Space}**. So getting, in **{Positional Continuity}**_{C}, the **{Glued Zones}**_{C}: **{Initial Widthwise Half Edge}**_{C} = **{IWHE}**_{C}, **{Final Widthwise Half Edge}**_{C} = **{FWHE}**_{C}. $\text{Length}_{\{S\}} = \text{Length}_{\{C\}}$; different lengths implying **{Glued Zones}**_{C} with Superposition, the remainder without Superposition: a **{param. 2-Manif. w.b.}** $\neq \{C\}$.
- 7.2) **{C}**. **{LFRA}**_{C} analyzes **{C}** naming it **{C}**. She senses:
 7.2.1) The devoid of superpositions **{Parametrization}**_{C}: a single **{Chart}**_{C} that precisely and entirely covers **{C}**. It contains **{IWHE}**_{C} \cup **{FWHE}**_{C}; they delimit one Circuit of **{C}**.
 7.2.2) **{Lengthwise Coordinate}**_{C}, **{Widthwise Coordinate}**_{C}: by those of **{S}**.
 7.2.3) **[Midline]**_{C} = $[\gamma_0]_{\{C\}}$ Closed Curve. It is geodesic, oriented, no-twist, at the **{Glued Zones}**_{C} with Positional Continuity and with a Frenet frame Continuity of a specified order. **{Initial Half Point}** = $[0 \rightarrow]$, **{Final Half Point}** = $\{\rightarrow 0\}$. In the **{Transformation: {S} \rightarrow {C}}**, the distinct **{End Half Points}**_{Midline_{S}}} = $\{[0 \rightarrow], \{\rightarrow 1\}\}$ fuse into the **{Final [Initial Point]}**_{Midline_{C}}} = $\{\rightarrow 0\} | [0 \rightarrow] = \{0\}$.
 7.2.4) The **[Intrinsic Boundary]**_{C} is a **[Closed Curve]**, with: a) two parallel, equally oriented by **{Maker-applied Arrows}**, **{Lengthwise Half Edges}**: $[\gamma_{\{B \rightarrow\}}]$, $[\gamma_{\{\rightarrow T\}}]$. b) Equally oriented by **{Orientation V}**: **{IWHE}**_{C} = $\{[0 \rightarrow] \times [\mathcal{V}_{\{0 \rightarrow\}}]\}$ _{C}, **{FWHE}**_{C} = $\{\{\rightarrow 0\} \times [\mathcal{V}_{\{\rightarrow 0\}}]\}$ _{C}.
 7.2.5) **[Oriented Intr. Boundary]** = $[[\mathcal{V}_{\{0 \rightarrow\}}], \gamma_{\{\rightarrow T\}}, -[\mathcal{V}_{\{\rightarrow 0\}}], -\gamma_{\{B \rightarrow\}}]_{\{C\}}$.
 7.2.6) Corresponding smooth **{Circ. Arrow vector field}**_{C}.
 7.2.7) Oriented **{C}**:
 $[[\{[0 \rightarrow] \times [\mathcal{V}_{\{0 \rightarrow\}}]\} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow \{\{u\} \times [\mathcal{V}_u]\} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow \{\{\rightarrow 0\} \times [\mathcal{V}_{\{\rightarrow 0\}}]\}]]_{\{C\}}$.
 7.2.8) Smooth **{Transitions in {C}}**: **{IWHE}**_{C} \leftrightarrow **{FWHE}**_{C}.
 7.2.9) A Number > 1 of **{LFRA}**_{C} - travelled circuits of **{C}** can be performed: not a property of **{C}**, but of **{Analysis Space}**_{C}. In a **{LFRA}**_{C}'s many-circuits travel, already travelled n.b.h.s appear with their previously noticed coordinate values, so she considers **{C}** a many-times seen, closed Cylinder.
 7.3) **{CC}**. The Maker got **{CC}** = **{C}** \cup **{C2}** by **{SS}** = **{S}** \cup **{S2}**, (see **{SS}**). From the point of view of a (Maker _{$\Delta_{\{R^3\}}$, t}) above **{FWHE}**_{C} \cup **{IWHE}**_{C}: he put in Contact, without **{Superposition: {S}, {S}}**, without **{Superposition: Verso {S2}, Verso {S2}}**, null Twist, and glued together, with a specified **{Parametric Continuity Order}**: **{IWHE}**_{S}, **{FWHE}**_{S}, getting **{Inner Widthwise**

Edge $_{\{C\}} = \{IWHE\}_{\{C\}} \cup \{FWHE\}_{\{C\}}$; Verso $\{IWHE\}_{\{S2\}}$, Verso $\{FWHE\}_{\{S2\}}$,
 getting Verso $\{\text{Inner Widthwise Edge}\}_{\{C2\}} = \text{Verso}\{IWHE\}_{\{C2\}} \cup \text{Verso}\{FWHE\}_{\{C2\}}$,
 Four $\{\text{Glued Zones}\}_{\{CC\}}$. Two-sheeted/sided, one cycle Cylinder.
 7.4) $\{CC\}$. The Maker's $\{CC\}$ is analyzed by $\{pLFRA\}_{\{CC\}}$ under the name $\{CC\}$.
 At her $\{\text{Residence Side}\}$, say $\{C\}$, $\{pLFRA\}_{\{CC\}} @ \{C\}$ senses:
 7.4.1) $\{\text{Superposition: } \{C\}, \text{Verso } \{C2\}\}$, including:
 $\{\text{Superposition: } \Delta C_u, \text{Verso } \Delta C2_u; \forall u\}$, $\{\text{Superposition: } \{IWHE\}_{\{C\}},$
 $\{IWHE\}_{\text{Verso } \{C2\}}\}$, $\{\text{Superposition: } \{FWHE\}_{\{C\}}, \{FWHE\}_{\text{Verso } \{C2\}}\}$,
 $\{\text{Superposition: } \{\text{Left Lengthwise Half Edge}\}_{\{C\}}, \{\text{Right L. H. Edge}\}_{\text{Verso } \{C2\}}\}$,
 $\{\text{Superposition: } \{\text{Right Lengthwise Half Edge}\}_{\{C\}}, \{\text{Left L. H. Edge}\}_{\text{Verso } \{C2\}}\}$,
 $\{\text{Superposition: } [\text{Oriented Intrinsic Boundary}]_{\{C\}}, [\text{Or. Intr. Boundary}]_{\text{Verso } \{C2\}}\}$.
 7.4.2) $\{\text{Circ. Arrow vector field}\}_{\text{Verso } \{C2\}} = -\{\text{Circ. Arrow vector field}\}_{\{C\}}$.
 7.4.3) Smooth $\{\text{Transitions in } \{C\}: \{IWHE\}_{\{C\}} \leftrightarrow \{FWHE\}_{\{C\}}\}$.
 Smooth $\{\text{Transition in Verso } \{C2\}: \{IWHE\}_{\text{Verso } \{C2\}} \leftrightarrow \{FWHE\}_{\text{Verso } \{C2\}}\}$.
 7.4.4) Non-smooth $\{\text{Transitions: } \{C\} \leftrightarrow \text{Verso } \{C2\}\}$.
 7.4.5) For $\{pLFRA\}_{\{CC\}}: \{CC\}$ is a closed two sheeted/sided Cylinder, one cycle.

8 $\{BMM\}$, $\{BMM\}$.

8.1) $\{BMM\}$. The Maker in $\{\mathbb{R}^{3+1}\}$ got the bare $\{BMM\}$ bending twisting
 $(\pi \text{ rad})$, gluing, with negligible stretching, a “Flat Rectangular Bare Strip” \equiv
 $\{BS\}$. “Bare” means that $\{BS\}$, and $\{BMM\}$, have not an intrinsic $\{\text{Structure}\}$.
 8.2) $\{BMM\}$. $\{pLFRA\}_{\{BMM\} \cup A}$ analyzes the abstract $\{BMM\}$, that cor-
 responds to the ambient $\{BMM\}$, within $\{\{BMM\} \cup \text{Associates}\}$, that is her
 $\{\text{Reference Space}\}$. Contrary to the usual, for this case of null Structure a set of
 not built-in references is introduced, i.e. an enlarged $\{\text{Reference Space}\}$, to get
 some information.
 The “Associates” of $\{BMM\}: \{\{pLFRA\}_{\{BMM\} \cup A}, \{OBIM\}_{\{BMM\} \cup A},$
 $\{\text{Markers}\}, \{\text{Instruments}\}\}$ are neither elements of $\{BMM\}$ nor of a Structure,
 8.2.1) $\{\text{Signal System}\}$. $\{pLFRA\}_{\{BMM\} \cup A}$ gets Signals from: a) $\{BMM\}$,
 b) $\{\text{Associates}\}$. Not Signals from the $\{\text{Complement Space}\}_{\{BMM\} \cup A}$.
 8.2.2) $\{\text{Analysis Space}\}_{\{BMM\} \cup A} = \{\{BMM\}, \{\text{Associates}\}, \{\text{Signal System}\}\}$.
 8.2.3) $\{pLFRA\}_{\{BMM\} \cup A}$ has Sight, Touch and the Senses of her own Gen.
 Curvatures.
 8.2.4) She adjusts herself strictly to her $\{BMM\}$'s local patch. Then she senses
 her own surface's properties, which equal local patch's properties. E.g., sensing
 her body's Gen. Curvatures, she senses the local $\{BMM\}$'s Gen. Curvatures.
 8.2.5) The $\{\text{Glued Zones}\}_{\{BMM\}}$ are recognized sensing their *special* Generalized
 Curvatures.
 8.2.6) $(pLFRA_{00})_{\{BMM\} \cup A}$ has her own built-in defined Directions & Orientations.
 Undefined Orientations of $\{BMM\}$.
 8.2.7) The initial state $(pLFRA_{00})_{\{BMM\} \cup A}$ has her Lengthwise Direction
 aligned to the $\{\text{Lengthwise Half Edges}\}_{\{BMM\}}$ ' Direction.

8.2.8) No need for the directed & oriented $\{\text{pLFRA}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\} \cup A}$ of leaning out of $\{\mathcal{BMM}\}$. She applies her $\{\text{Boundary Instruments}\}$ and by them reveals two parallel, superposed, closed, not parametrized $\{\text{Intrinsic Boundary Lengthwise Curves}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\}}$: the $\{\text{Left Lengthwise Half Edge}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\}}$, always at her left; the $\{\text{Right Lengthwise Half Edge}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\}}$ always at her right. They do not send signals. Their Markers do. Recognizing Superposition of Markers lead to recognizing Superposition of the $\{\text{Lengthwise Half Edges}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\}}$.

So that $\{\text{pLFRA}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\} \cup A}$ considers $\{\mathcal{BMM}\}$ a $\{2\text{-Manif. with boundary}\}$.
 8.2.9) Any $\{\text{Reception n.b.h.}\} = \Delta\{\mathcal{BMM}\}$ does not send signals from a $\{\text{Chart}\}$: it is lacking. *But it is $\{\text{pLFRA}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\} \cup A}$ -sensed* by Sight, Touch, ..., by the bodily-measured values of Curvature and Torsion. Eventually, a $\{\text{pLFRA}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\} \cup A}$ -placed $\{\text{Marker}\}$ is detected in it.

8.2.10) At a previously recognized $\{\text{Glued Zone}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\}}$, $(\text{pLFRA}_{00})_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\} \cup A}$ puts an $\{\text{Origin Marker}\}$. Travelling, $\{\text{pLFRA}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\} \cup A}$ senses Verso $\{\text{Origin Marker}\}$, and continuing she detects $\{\text{Origin Marker}\}$ again, implying $\{\text{Smooth Transitions}\}$ of $\{\mathcal{BMM}\}$ along the $\{\text{Lengthwise Half Edges}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\}}$ ' Direction.

8.2.11) Already travelled patches, with memorized Textures, Gen. Curvatures and Markers, are smoothly reached and recognized: $\{\mathcal{BMM}\}$ is closed.

8.2.12) $\{\text{pLFRA}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\} \cup A}$ can have, for example: a) $\{\text{Reception non-parametrized n.b.h.}\} = \Delta\{\mathcal{BMM}\}_0 \cup \{\text{Origin Marker}\}$. b) $\{\text{Reception non-parametrized n.b.h.}\} = \Delta\{\mathcal{BMM}\}_m$ and its $\{\text{Superposed n.b.h.}\} = \text{Verso}\{\text{Origin Marker}\}$. By $\{a + b\}$, $\{\text{pLFRA}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\} \cup A}$ recognizes the two-sheetness of $\{\mathcal{BMM}\}$.

8.2.13) Assuming $\{\text{OBIM}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\} \cup A}$ as a $\{\text{Mobile Marker}\}$, a generic

$(\text{pLFRA}_{\Delta\{\mathcal{BMM}\}t}) @ \Delta\{\mathcal{BMM}\}$ can have as $\{\text{Perception N.B.H.}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\} \cup A}$:

either a) $\Delta\{\mathcal{BMM}\} \cup (\text{pLFRA}_{\Delta\{\mathcal{BMM}\}t}) @ \Delta\{\mathcal{BMM}\}$ or

b) $\Delta\{\mathcal{BMM}\} \cup \{ (\text{pLFRA}_{\Delta\{\mathcal{BMM}\}t}) \cup (\text{OBIM}_{\Delta\{\mathcal{BMM}\}t}) \} @ \Delta\{\mathcal{BMM}\}$

or c) $\Delta\{\mathcal{BMM}\} \cup (\text{pLFRA}_{\Delta\{\mathcal{BMM}\}t}) @ \Delta\{\mathcal{BMM}\} \cup \text{Verso}(\text{OBIM}_{\Delta\{\mathcal{BMM}\}t})$.

8.2.14) A kind of Positional Continuity in $\{\mathcal{BMM}\}$, in absence of an available Mathematical Structure.

8.2.15) $\{\text{pLFRA}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\}}$ does not sense unreachable Subsurfaces; she senses the unique $\{\text{Side}\}_{\{\mathcal{BMM}\}}$.

9 $\{\text{MC}\}, \{\text{MC}\}$

9.1) $\{\text{MC}\}$. With $\{\text{Reference Space}\} = \{\mathbb{R}^3\}$, the Maker dubbed $\{\text{MC}\}$ the Ruled Surface got by bending, twisting ($\theta \text{ rad}; 0 < \theta < \pi$), a rectangular $\mathcal{L} \times \ell_0$ flat parametrized Strip $\{\mathcal{S}\}$, joining: $\{\text{Final Half Point}\}_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$, $\{\text{Initial Half Point}\}_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$ of $[\text{Midline}]_{\{\mathcal{S}\}}$. The Maker recognizes consequently for $\{\text{MC}\}$, length \mathcal{L} : Contact in $\{\text{Complement Space}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}} \subset \{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ of $\{\text{End Half Points}\}_{[\text{Midline}]_{\{\text{MC}\}}}$, (no interposition of $\{\text{Complement Space}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}$ within them, no superposition of them): the $\{\text{Final Half Point}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}} = \{\rightarrow 1\} \subset \{\text{Final Widthwise Half Edge}\} = \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}$ and the $\{\text{Initial Half Point}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}} = [0 \rightarrow] \subset \{\text{Initial Widthwise Half Edge}\} = \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}$. According to the Maker: $[\text{Midline}]_{\{\text{MC}\}}$'s $\{\text{Positional Continuity in } \{\mathbb{R}^3\}\}$. Scarce $F^{-1}[\text{Midline}]_{\{\text{MC}\}}$'s $\{\text{Frenet frame Continuity}\}$ in the Maker's construct: Continuity of \mathbf{t}, κ, τ ; Discontinuity of \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{b} .

- 9.1.1) A unique $\{\text{Chart}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}$ covers $\{\text{MC}\}$ entirely.
- 9.1.2) Lengthwise Coordinate $[u]_{\{\text{MC}\}}$. Along Ruling Coordinate $[v]_{\{\text{MC}\}}$.
- 9.1.3) Indexed by $[u]_{\{\text{MC}\}}$, Vector Field $\{[\mathbf{V}]\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}$. $[\mathbf{V}_u]_{\{\text{MC}\}}$ along Ruling u .
- 9.2) $\{\text{MC}\}$. $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}$ analyzes the Maker's $\{\text{MC}\}$ under the name $\{\text{MC}\}$.
- 9.2.1) $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}$ makes reference to the $\{\text{MC}\}$ Space.
- 9.2.2) Not sensed Superpositions of n.b.h.s \longrightarrow one-sheeted $\{\text{MC}\}$ for her.
Not sensed unreachable Sides of $\{\text{MC}\}$ \longrightarrow one-sided $\{\text{MC}\}$ for her.
- 9.2.3) $[\text{Midline}]_{\{\text{MC}\}} = [\gamma_0]_{\{\text{MC}\}} : [[0 \rightarrow], \{\rightarrow 1\}] \in \{\mathbb{R} \rightarrow\} \rightarrow \{\text{MC}\}$.
- 9.2.4) For the directed and oriented $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}$ in $\{\text{MC}\}$:
 $\{\text{Left Lengthwise Internal Half Edge}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}$, $\{\text{Right Lengthwise Internal Half Edge}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}$ are $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}$ -sensed by $\{\text{Boundary Instruments}\}$, distinguishing: signal-emitting $\{\text{MC}\}$, by assumption not signal-emitting $\{\text{Complement Space}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}$.
- 9.2.5) $\{\text{Initial Widthwise Half Edge}\} = \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}} = [[0 \rightarrow] \times [V_{[0 \rightarrow]}]]_{\{\text{MC}\}}$,
 $\{\text{Final Widthwise Half Edge}\} = \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}} = [\{\rightarrow 1\} \times [V_{\{\rightarrow 1\}}]]_{\{\text{MC}\}}$.
- 9.2.6) Smooth $\{\text{Transitions: } \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}} \xleftarrow{\text{within } \{\text{MC}\}} \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}\}$,
Non-smooth in $\{\text{MC}\}$:
 $\{\text{Transitions: } \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}} \xleftarrow{\text{in } \{\text{Complement Space}\}} \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}\}$.
- 9.2.7) So that the initial state ($\text{LFRA}_{\Delta \text{MC}_{[0 \rightarrow]} 0}$) cannot sense $\{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}$.
So that the final state ($\text{LFRA}_{\Delta \text{MC}_{\{\rightarrow 1\}} f}$) cannot sense $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}$.
- 9.2.8) The initial state ($\text{LFRA}_{\Delta \text{MC}_{[0 \rightarrow]} 0}$) senses
 $\Delta \text{MC}_{[0 \rightarrow]} \supset \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}} \supset \{\text{Initial Half Point}\}_{[\text{Midline}]} = [0 \rightarrow]$.
- 9.2.9) The final state ($\text{LFRA}_{\Delta \text{MC}_{\{\rightarrow 1\}} f}$) senses
 $\Delta \text{MC}_{\{\rightarrow 1\}} \supset \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}} \supset \{\text{Final Half Point}\}_{[\text{Midline}]} = \{\rightarrow 1\}$.
- 9.2.10) (Symbolism. Not the $\{\text{Initial \& Final Point}\} = \{\rightarrow 0 \parallel 0 \rightarrow\} = \{0\}$, that denotes Parametric Continuity and Smooth Transitions in a [Closed Curve].)
- 9.2.11) The initial state ($\text{LFRA}_{\Delta \text{MC}_{[0 \rightarrow]} 0}$) does not sense $\{\rightarrow 1\}$.
- 9.2.12) The final state ($\text{LFRA}_{\Delta \text{MC}_{\{\rightarrow 1\}} f}$) does not sense $[0 \rightarrow]$.
- 9.2.13) Hence they do not sense, since not in the $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}}$ -travelled & defined $\{\text{MC}\}$, the $\{\text{Contact in } \{\text{Complement Space}\}_{\{\text{MC}\}} \text{ of: } \{\rightarrow 1\}, [0 \rightarrow]\}$.

10 $\{\mathbb{M}\}$, $\{\mathbb{M}\}$, $\{\text{Me}\}$, $\{\text{RM}\}$, $\{\text{TM}\}$

- 10.1) The $\{\text{Maker}\}$ made $\{\mathbb{M}\}$ $\{\text{Möbius strip}\}$ bending, twisting $\pi \text{ rad}$ an one-sheeted one-sided structured, directed & oriented rectangular $\mathcal{L} \times \ell_0$ Strip $\{\text{S}\}$, with a single $\{\text{Chart}\}_{\{\text{S}\}}$. From the point of view of the (Maker state #1 in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ above $\{\text{Initial Widthwise Half Edge}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}$) and according to him: he joined without superposition and glued the Verso $\{\text{Final Widthwise Half Edge}\}_{\{\text{S}\}}$ to the $\{\text{Initial Widthwise Half Edge}\}_{\{\text{S}\}}$ into the
 $\{\text{Glued Zones}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}} = \{\text{Verso } \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}} \subset \text{Verso } \Delta \mathbb{M}_f, \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}} \subset \Delta \mathbb{M}_0\}$.
- 10.2) Without looking out of $\{\mathbb{M}\}$, the $\{\text{Maker}\}$ does not sense Superpositions in $\{\mathbb{M}\}$. Sensing at the $\{\text{Glued Zones}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}$ he senses a Recto N.B.H. and a Verso N.B.H.; that means two-sheetness.

- 10.3) $\{\text{Chart}\}_{\{S\}} \rightsquigarrow \{\text{Chart}\}_{\{M\}}$, that covers $\{M\}$ entirely without superpositions.
- 10.4) (A $\{\text{Superposition: } \{\Delta\text{Chart}\}_{\text{Verso } \Delta M_f}, \{\Delta\text{Chart}\}_{\Delta M_0}\}$ and a single $\{\text{Chart}\}$ for the remainder implies another kind of Geometric Object.)
- 10.5) The $\{\text{Chart}\}_{\{S\}}$'s Origin was at the $\{\text{Initial Widthwise Half Edge}\}_{\{S\}}$. Hence the chosen, ensuing $\{\text{Chart}\}_{\{M\}}$'s Origin is at the $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}}$.
- 10.6) $\text{Length}_{\{S\}} = \text{Length}_{\{\text{Chart}\}_{\{S\}}} = \mathcal{L} = \text{Length}_{\{M\}} = \text{Length}_{\{\text{Chart}\}_{\{M\}}}$.
- 10.7) By **I2** ✘. A single $\{\text{Chart}\}_{\{M\}}$ implies a smooth $\{\text{Structure}\}_{\{M\}}$.
- 10.8) A smooth $\{\text{Structure}\}_{\{M\}}$ implies a smooth $\{M\}$. [14]
- 10.9) The (Maker state #1) recognizes Verso $\{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}}$ as Verso $\{\text{Final Half Ruling}\}_{\{M\}}$ and $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}}$ as $\{\text{Initial Half Ruling}\}_{\{M\}}$.
- 10.10) Geodesic $[\text{Midline}]_{\{M\}} = [\gamma_0]_{\{M\}} = [\gamma_{\{ \rightarrow 0 \}}]_{\{M\}} \cup [\gamma_{\{ 0 \rightarrow \}}]_{\{M\}}$.
In the along Ruling's $[v]_{\{M\}}$ coordinate: $\{ \rightarrow v \} = \{ \rightarrow 0 \}$; $[v \rightarrow \} = [0 \rightarrow \}$.
I.e. two adjacent parallel not closed Curves each one \mathcal{L} long, with Endpoints at the $\{\text{Glued Zones}\}_{\{M\}}$.
- 10.10.1) No straight segments in $\{ \text{Int} [\text{Midline}]_{\{M\}} \}$. [22] [23]
- 10.10.2) The $\{\text{Frenet frame field}\}$ is continuous in $\text{Int} [\gamma_{\{ \rightarrow 0 \}}]$ and in $\text{Int} [\gamma_{\{ 0 \rightarrow \}}]$.
- 10.10.3) The (Maker state #1) senses **non-smooth contacts** of $[\gamma_{\{ \rightarrow 0 \}}]$, $[\gamma_{\{ 0 \rightarrow \}}]$:
Verso $\{\text{Final Half Point}\} = \text{Verso } \gamma_{0 \rightarrow}(\rightarrow 1)$ with $\gamma_{0 \rightarrow}(0 \rightarrow) = \{\text{Initial Half Point}\}$.
Verso $\{\text{Final Half Point}\} = \text{Verso } \gamma_{0 \rightarrow}(\rightarrow 1)$ with $\gamma_{0 \rightarrow}(0 \rightarrow) = \{\text{Initial Half Point}\}$.
At the $\{\text{Glued Zones}\}_{\{M\}}$. That implies: these Curves are not closed.
- 10.11) **$\{\text{Darboux frame field}\} = \{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{u}, \nu\}$** for $[\gamma_0]$. Locally $\{\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{u}\} \subset \{\text{Tangent Plane}\}$; $\nu \perp \{M\}$; At $\{\text{Glued Zones}\}_{\{M\}}$: Continuous $[\mathbf{t}]$, discontinuous $[\mathbf{u}]$, $[\nu]$.
- 10.12) Within $\{M\}$, for any ΔM_i following ΔM_0 and preceding ΔM_f , any (Maker state # i in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ above ΔM_i) senses a Sequence:
 $\{ \{\text{Recto preceding n.b.h.}\} , \{ \text{Recto n.b.h.}_i \} , \{ \text{Recto following n.b.h.}\} \}$.
- 10.12.1) That implies: smooth $\{ \text{Transitions: } \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}} \xleftarrow{\text{in } \{M\}} \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}} \}$;
- $\{\text{Parametric Continuity: } \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}} \xleftarrow{\text{In } \{M\}} \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}} \}$** .
- 10.13) **$\{\text{Glued Zones}\}_{\{M\}}$** . They satisfy the Randrup & Røgen property, that we call the Rectangular Strip Condition: zero Curvature, that flips; zero Torsion.
Angle: $[\text{Initial } [\mathbf{t}], \{\text{Initial Ruling}\}] = \pi/2$;
 $[\text{Final } [\mathbf{t}], \text{Verso } \{\text{Final Ruling}\}] = -\pi/2$. [20]
- 10.13.1) No interposed $\{\text{Complement Space}\}_{\{M\}}$ in the $\{\text{Glued Zones}\}_{\{M\}}$.
- 10.14) (Maker state # 1 in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ above $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}}$)'s sensations.
- 10.14.1) $\{\text{Circ. Arrow}\}_{\text{Verso } \Delta M_f} = - \{\text{Circ. Arrow}\}_{\Delta M_0}$.
- 10.14.2) Verso $\{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}}$, $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}}$ are distant in $\{M\}$, adjacent in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$.
- 10.14.3) Verso $\{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}}$, $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}}$: equal Widthwise Direction, opposite Widthwise Orientation.
- 10.14.4) Since Verso ΔM_f , ΔM_0 are distant in $\{M\}$, then: a) The comparison of the partial derivatives of Verso ΔM_f , ΔM_0 is of no interest.
b) The $\{\text{Parametric Continuity in } \{M\}\}$ for Verso ΔM_f , ΔM_0 is of no interest.
- 10.14.5) Obviously the living in $\{M\}$ - $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$ cannot perform the
 $\{ \text{Jump Transitions: } \text{Verso } \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}} \xleftarrow{\text{in } \{\text{Complement Space}\}} \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}} \}$.
- 10.15) Similar sensations for the (Maker state #2 in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ above $\{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}}$),

- 10.16) Corresponding to the **{Glued Zones}**_{M}, the Maker senses some amount of **{Parametric Continuity in {R³}**: a **{Self-Contact of {M} in {R³}**.
- 10.17) **Summary.** The Maker senses {M} with specific Terminals: Verso {FWHE}_{M}, {IWHE}_{M}. And their mutual, non-smooth Contact. Similarly, {M} with Terminals: Verso {IWHE}_{M}, {FWHE}_{M}. I.e. a Self-Contact of {M} in {R³}.
- 10.18) **Appendix.** The *{Intrinsic Observer}*_{M} cannot jump. (Maker state #1) about { Jump Transitions: Verso $\Delta M_f \xleftarrow{\text{in } \{\text{Complement Space}\}} \Delta M_0$ }.
- The following equality was assumed, facilitating comparisons:
{Circ. Arrow} (Intr. Observer Verso ΔM_f) @ Verso ΔM_f = **{Circ. Arrow}** Verso ΔM_f .
- The jumping (Intr. Observer Verso ΔM_f t) @ Verso ΔM_f goes out of Verso ΔM_f into {Compl. Space}_{M}, rotates, re-enters {M} as (Intr. Observer ΔM_0 t+ δt) @ ΔM_0 ;
 $\xrightarrow{\text{after said movement}}$ **{Circ. Arrow}** (Intr. Observer ΔM_0 t+ δt) @ ΔM_0 = **{Circ. Arrow}** ΔM_0 .
- 10.19) **{M}**. According to the {Maker}: {LFRA}_{M}, and the {LFRA}_{M} - analyzed {M} are, immersed in {R³}, {R²} Objects.
- 10.20) {LFRA}_{M} performs an intrinsic analysis of {M}, that corresponds to the {Maker}'s {M}, using *only intrinsically obtainable informations*.
- 10.21) **{Relations: {M}, {LFRA}_{M}}**. By definition: {LFRA}_{M} remains within the {Intrinsic Boundary}_{M}, without sensing outside it.
- 10.21) A report of the {LFRA}_{M}'s analysis follows.
- 10.22) A generic (LFRA_{ut})_{M} @ ΔM_u has: {Perception N.B.H.} = {Reception n.b.h.} = ΔM_u ; no {Superposed n.b.h.}, no {Glanced n.b.h.}.
- 10.22.1) No {Superposed n.b.h.} implies: {M} is a regular Surface.
- 10.22.2) (LFRA_{[0→]0})_{M} has {Perception N.B.H.} = $\Delta M_{[0→]} \supset \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}}$.
- 10.22.3) (LFRA_{{→1}f})_{M} has {Perception N.B.H.} = $\Delta M_{\{→1\}} \supset \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}}$.
- 10.22.4) A clarification. Not in the {LFRA}_{M}'s Perceptions: Verso $\Delta M_{[0→]}$, ..., Verso ΔM_u , ..., Verso $\Delta M_{\{→1\}}$.
- 10.23) **{Associates}** = { {LFRA}_{M}, {OBIM}_{M}, {Instruments} }.
- 10.23.1) (LFRA_{ut})_{M}'s {Perception N.B.H.}_{M} may be: ..., $\Delta M_u \cup (\text{LFRA}_{ut}) @ \Delta M_u$; $\Delta M_u \cup \{ (\text{LFRA}_{ut}) \cup (\text{OBIM}_{ut}) \} @ \Delta M_u$; $\Delta M_u \cup \{ (\text{LFRA}_{ut}) \cup \text{Verso}(\text{OBIM}_{ut}) \} @ \Delta M_u$ where Verso(OBIM_{ut}) \notin {M} borrows the parameter value of ΔM_u .
- 10.24) For convenience, a Maker - done single {Chart}_{M} covers the entire {M}.
- 10.25) Lengthwise Coordinate [u]_{M}. Along Ruling Coordinate [v]_{M}.
- 10.26) **Field**{ **{Twin Parallel Lengthwise Curves}**_{M} } = Representation of the Map { γ }_{M} : [[0→], {→1}] × [[B→], {→T}] → {M}. [Lengthwise Coordinate] \supset [0→] = [Initial H. Point], {→1} = [Final H. Point]. [Ruling Coordinate] \supset [B→] = [Bottom Half Point], {→T} = [Top Half Point]. {Twin P. Lengthwise Curves} have [Orientation L] by *{Maker-applied Arrows}*, are lengthwise bounded by {IWHE}_{M}, {FWHE}_{M}. Each Curve has Length \mathcal{L} .
- 10.27) **{Generic Twin Parallel Lengthwise Curves}**_{M}. Representation of { γ_v }_{M} = { [$\gamma - v/2$], [$\gamma v/2$] }_{M}; $\ell = \ell(u)$; $v(u) = v_0 \ell / \ell_0$; $\forall u$.
- 10.28) **{Centre Twin Parallel Lengthwise Curves}** = [Midline]_{M} = { γ_0 }_{M}. [$\gamma_{\{→0\}}$] having { -v/2 } = { → 0 }. [$\gamma_{[0→]}$] having { v/2 } = [0 →]. So that:

$\{\gamma_0\}_{\{M\}} = \{[\gamma_{\{0 \rightarrow\}}], [\gamma_{\{0 \rightarrow\}}]\}_{\{M\}}: [[0 \rightarrow], \{\rightarrow 1\}] \times \{\{ \rightarrow 0\}, [0 \rightarrow]\} \rightarrow \{M\}$.

10.28.1) $[\gamma_{\{0 \rightarrow\}}]$, length \mathcal{L} , is not a Closed Path in $\{M\}$, since:

$$[\gamma_{\{0 \rightarrow\}}] \cap \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}} = \{[\mathbf{0} \rightarrow] \times [0 \rightarrow]\} \neq$$

$$[\gamma_{\{0 \rightarrow\}}] \cap \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}} = \{[\rightarrow \mathbf{1}] \times [0 \rightarrow]\}.$$

10.28.2) Similarly for $[\gamma_{\{\rightarrow 0\}}]$.

10.28.3) **Symbolism in $[\text{Midline}]_{\{M\}}$:** Initial Half Point $[0 \rightarrow]$, Final Half Point $\{\rightarrow 1\}$. Not $\{\rightarrow 0\}[0 \rightarrow]$ that denotes Continuity of a Closed Path.

10.29) **$\{\text{Twin Parallel Lengthwise Curves of the Intrinsic Boundary}\}_{\{M\}}$:**

$$\{\gamma_{B \rightarrow T}\}_{\{M\}} = \{[\gamma_{B \rightarrow}], [\gamma_{\rightarrow T}]\}_{\{M\}}. \quad \text{Where:}$$

$$[\gamma_{B \rightarrow}] = [\text{Bottom Half Points Locus}] ; [\gamma_{\rightarrow T}] = [\text{Top Half Points Locus}].$$

$$10.30) \{\text{Ruled Surface Vector Field}\} = \{[\mathbf{V}]\}_{\{M\}}.$$

10.30.1) **Generic $\{\text{Ruling Vector}\} = [\mathbf{V}_u]_{\{M\}} \subset \{[\mathbf{V}]\}_{\{M\}}$.** Along $\{\text{Ruling}\}_u$.

10.30.2) **Generic $\{\text{Ruling Segment}\} = \|\mathbf{V}_u\|_{\{M\}} = \ell(u); \ell \neq \ell_0$.** [22] [23] [27].

10.30.3) $(\text{LFRA}_{\{0 \rightarrow\} 0})_{\{M\}}$ senses **$\{\text{Initial Half Ruling Vector}\} = [\mathbf{V}_{\{0 \rightarrow\}}]_{\{M\}}$.**

10.30.4) $(\text{LFRA}_{\{\rightarrow 1\} f})_{\{M\}}$ senses **$\{\text{Final Half Ruling Vector}\} = [\mathbf{V}_{\{\rightarrow 1\}}]_{\{M\}}$.**

10.30.5) **$[\text{Orientation L}]$ of $\{[\mathbf{V}]\}_{\{M\}} = [\text{Orientation L}]$ of $[u]_{\{M\}}$.**

10.30.6) **Arrangement in $\{M\}$ along $[u]_{\{M\}}$ of adjacent Ruling Vectors,** for small ℓ/\mathcal{L} : Bottom near Bottom, Top near Top. Smooth $\{[\mathbf{V}]\}_{\{M\}}$ within $\{M\}$.

10.30.7) **$[\text{Orientation V}]$ of any generic $[\mathbf{V}_u]_{\{M\}}$:**

Bottom Point \rightarrow Midpoint \rightarrow Top Point i.e. $[B \rightarrow] \{\rightarrow 0 \rightarrow\} \{\rightarrow T\}$.

10.30.8) **$[\text{Orientation L} \times \mathbf{V}]$ of the Points of $\{[\mathbf{V}]\}_{\{M\}}$:** a Dictionary Order. [17]

10.31) **$\{\text{Angle } \beta : t, [\mathbf{V}_u]_{\{M\}}\}$.** It is function of the local Curvature and Torsion.

10.32) **$\{M\}$'s Intrinsic Sheetness.** Locally, any state $(\text{LFRA}_{ut})_{\{M\}} @ \Delta M_u$, inclusive of $\Delta M_{\{0 \rightarrow\}}$ and $\Delta M_{\{\rightarrow 1\}}$, does not sense *superposed* $\{\text{n.b.h.s}\}_{\{M\}}$.

(Either $\{\text{OBIM}\}_{\{M\}}$ or Verso $\{\text{OBIM}\}_{\{M\}}$ can be sensed, but they are not of $\{M\}$). Globally, for definition, $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$ senses one-sheetness of $\{M\}$.

10.33) Ignoring **Thickness**, $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$ can't say that $\{M\}$ has null Thickness.

10.34) **Directions & Orientations.** In her analysis of $\{M\}$, $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$ uses her Directions & Orientations to assess the Directions & Orientations of $\{M\}$.

10.34.1) The Directions & Orientations that the Maker gave $\{M\}$, and marked in $\{M\}$, are $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$ -perceived as elements of the intrinsic $\{\text{Structure}\}_{\{M\}}$.

10.34.2) $(\text{LFRA}_{\{0 \rightarrow\} 0})_{\{M\}}$ Initial state's built-in $\{\text{Aft} \rightarrow \text{Front}$, and $\text{Left} \rightarrow \text{Right}$, Directions & Orientations $\}$ are equalized to those of the Initial $\Delta M_{\{0 \rightarrow\}}$.

10.34.3) $(\text{LFRA}_{ut})_{\{M\}}$ state's $\text{Aft} \rightarrow \text{Front}$, and $\text{Left} \rightarrow \text{Right}$ Directions & Orientations are kept equal to those of $\Delta M_u; \forall u$ in $\{M\}$.

10.34.4) Momentary shifts from this equality of the $(\text{LFRA}_{ut})_{\{M\}}$'s Directions & Orientations to those of ΔM_u are necessary for the analysis of $\{M\}$.

10.35) **$\{\text{Circ. Arrow field}\}_{\{M\}}$.**

10.35.1) $\{M\}$ is smooth, hence smooth $\{\text{Circ. Arrow vector field}\}_{\{M\}}$ in $\{M\}$.

10.35.2) A Maker's convenient **Assumption** for $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$:

Initial $\{\text{Circ. Arrow}\}_{(\text{LFRA}_{\{0 \rightarrow\} 0})_{\{M\}}} = \{\text{Circ. Arrow}\}_{\Delta M_{\{0 \rightarrow\}}}$.

10.35.3) $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$ is in continuous adhering contact with $\{M\}$.

- 10.35.4) By the above: $\{\text{Circ. Arrow}\}_{(\text{LFRA}_{ut})_{\{M\}}} = \{\text{Circ. Arrow}\}_{\Delta M_u}; \forall u.$
- 10.36) **Twist of $\{M\}$.** Let $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$ have a built-in Sensor of her own Torsion, or equivalent Instruments. By the strict $\{\text{Superposition: } (\text{LFRA}_{ut})_{\{M\}}, \Delta M_u\}$, the $(\text{LFRA}_{ut})_{\{M\}}$'s Torsion equals the Torsion of ΔM_u . The local Torsion is measured. Integrating it, $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$ can perceive the Twist of $\{M\}$.
- 10.37) **Lengthwise Half Edges facing on Int $\{M\}$** $\}_{\{M\}} = \{[\gamma_{B \rightarrow}], [\gamma_{T \rightarrow}]\}$. They are the $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$ -sensed insides of the $\{\text{Lengthwise Edges}\}_{\{M\}}$.
- 10.38) **Widthwise Half Edges facing on Int $\{M\}$** $\}_{\{M\}}$. They are the $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$ -sensed insides of the $\{\text{Widthwise Edges}\}_{\{M\}}$:
 $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}} = [\mathbf{V}_{\{0 \rightarrow\}}]_{\{M\}} \subset \Delta M_{\{0 \rightarrow\}}, \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}} = [\mathbf{V}_{\{ \rightarrow 1\}}]_{\{M\}} \subset \Delta M_{\{ \rightarrow 1\}}.$
- 10.38.1) $\{M\}$ is between $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}}, \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}}$, including them.
- 10.38.2) $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}}, \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}}$ confine $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$ within $\{M\}$, to maintain her $\{M\}$ -intrinsic.
- 10.39) **Oriented Intrinsic Boundary** $\}_{\{M\}}$. By Maker - Induced Orientation. $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$ senses: $\{[\mathbf{V}_{\{0 \rightarrow\}}], [\gamma_{T \rightarrow}], -[\mathbf{V}_{\{ \rightarrow 1\}}], -[\gamma_{B \rightarrow}]\}_{\{M\}}$.
- 10.40) $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$ cannot go out of, and sense out of $\{M\}$. E.g.:
 $(\text{LFRA}_{\Delta M_{\{0 \rightarrow\}}})$ cannot sense, because they are not in $\{M\}$:
 Verso ΔM_u , Verso $\{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}}, \{\text{Contact: } \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}}, \text{Verso } \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}}\}$.
 $(\text{LFRA}_{\Delta M_{\{ \rightarrow 1\}}})$ cannot sense, because they are not in $\{M\}$:
 Verso ΔM_u , Verso $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}}, \{\text{Contact: } \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}}, \text{Verso } \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}}\}$.
- 10.41) $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$'s **Smooth Transitions:** $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}} \xleftarrow{\text{within } \{M\}} \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}}$.
- 10.42) $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$ cannot effect:
 $\{\text{Jump Transitions: Verso } \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}} \xleftarrow{\text{in } \{\text{Compl. Space}\}} \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}}\};$
 $\{\text{Jump Transitions: Verso } \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}} \xleftarrow{\text{in } \{\text{Compl. Space}\}} \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}}\}.$
- 10.43) **Transitions in $\{MW\}$.** (see $\{MW\}$) A $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{MW\}}$ can effect Transitions in $\{MW\}$ between $\{M\}$ and a non-parametrized $\{W\}$. But for a $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{M\}}$, they imply the loss of her "intrinsic attribute":
 $\{\text{Transitions: } \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}} \xleftarrow{\text{along } [t]} \Delta (\text{Bare Manifold})\}.$
 $\{\text{Transitions: } \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}} \xleftarrow{\text{along } [-t]} \Delta (\text{Bare Manifold})\}.$
- 10.44) The **Parametric Continuity** $\}_{\{M\}}$ is assured in $\{M\}$ and ends at the $\{\text{Glued Zones}\}_{\{M\}}$. $\{M\}$ is well defined lengthwise.
- 10.45) It is not necessary to cut $\{M\}$ to make it orientable.
- 10.46) An *Extrinsic Observer* may compare $\{C\}, \{M\}$: both have one Sheet, one Side.
- 10.47) **Me**. A *Möbius strip* $\{\text{Me}\}$ having parallel, oppositely oriented hence non-identifiable, *superposed*: $\{\text{Initial Widthwise Edge}\}_{\{\text{Me}\}}, \text{Verso } \{\text{Final Widthwise Edge}\}_{\{\text{Me}\}}$ is not $\{M\}$. According to the Maker in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ above the $\{\text{Glued Zones}\}_{\{\text{Me}\}}$: one-Sheetness at $\{\text{Me}\} \setminus \{ \{ \{0\} \times [V_0] \}, \text{Verso } \{ \{1\} \times [V_1] \} \}$, two-Sheetness at $\{ \{ \{0\} \times [V_0] \}, \text{Verso } \{ \{1\} \times [V_1] \} \}$.
- 10.48) The one-sided *Möbius strip* **RM** is got by a Rhomboidal Strip **RS**: no $[t]$ -Continuity at the adjoined $\{\text{Widthwise Half Edges}\}_{\{\text{RM}\}}$.
- 10.49) The one-sided *Möbius strip* **TM** is got by a Trapezoidal Strip **TS**.

11 $\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}$, $\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}$, $\{\mathcal{M}\mathbb{W}\}$

11.1) $\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}$. The Maker bent, twisted π rad and glued together $\{\text{Initial Edge}\}$, $\{\text{Final Edge}\}$ of $\{\text{SZ}\}$, the superposition of two, both recognizable, rectangular $\mathcal{L} \times \ell_0$ Strips: the parametrized $\{\text{S}\}$ and $\{\text{Z}\}$ that has not its own Parametrization. According to him, getting the two-sheeted one-sided $\{2\text{-Manif. w.b.}\} = \{\{\mathbb{M}\}, \{\mathbb{W}\}\} = \{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}$. $\{\mathbb{M}\}$, having $\{\text{Structure}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}$ with a single $\{\text{Chart}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}$; $\{\mathbb{W}\}$ without a Structure: no Chart. Maker refers either to $\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}$ or to $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$.

11.2) $\{\text{Glued Zones}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}}: \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}, \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}, \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{W}\}}, \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{W}\}}$.

11.2.1) The (Maker state #1 in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ above $\{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{W}\}} \cup \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}$) senses:

- a) $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}, \{\text{Superposition: } \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{W}\}}; \text{Verso } \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}\}$
- b) $\{\text{Non-smooth Contact in } \{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}: \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}, \text{Verso } \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}\}$.
- c) $\{\text{Positional Continuity in } \{\mathbb{R}^3\}: \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}, \text{Verso } \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}\}$.

It means that Verso $\{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}, \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}$ are adjacent in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$.

11.2.2) The (Maker state #2 in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ above $\{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}} \cup \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{W}\}}$) senses similarly.

11.3) The Maker in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ senses:

smooth $\{\text{Transitions: } \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}} \xleftarrow{\text{in } \{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}} \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{W}\}}\}$,

smooth $\{\text{Transitions: } \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{W}\}} \xleftarrow{\text{in } \{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}} \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}\}$.

Not possible, not smooth in $\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}$:

$\{\text{Jump Transitions: Verso } \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}} \xleftarrow{\text{in } \{\text{ComplementSpace}\}} \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}\}$,

$\{\text{Jump Transitions: Verso } \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}} \xleftarrow{\text{in } \{\text{ComplementSpace}\}} \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}\}$.

$\{\text{Jump Transitions: Verso } \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{W}\}} \xleftarrow{\text{in } \{\text{ComplementSpace}\}} \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{W}\}}\}$,

$\{\text{Jump Transitions: Verso } \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{W}\}} \xleftarrow{\text{in } \{\text{ComplementSpace}\}} \{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{W}\}}\}$.

11.4) **Generic $\{\text{Twin Parallel Lengthwise Curves}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}} = \{[\gamma - v/2], [\gamma v/2]\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}$.**

11.4.1) $\{\mathcal{L}\}$ long $[\gamma - v/2]_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}$. At a distance $\{\mathcal{L}, v\}$ in $\{\mathbb{M}\}$, its:

$\{\text{Initial Half Point}\}$ on $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}$, $\{\text{Final Half Point}\}$ on $\{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}$.

11.4.2) $\{\mathcal{L}\}$ long $[\gamma v/2]_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}$. At a distance $\{\mathcal{L}, v\}$ in $\{\mathbb{M}\}$, its:

$\{\text{Initial Half Point}\}$ on $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}$, $\{\text{Final Half Point}\}$ on $\{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}}$.

11.5) (If the Maker needs a better definition for $\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}$, he extends the Parametrization to $\{\mathbb{W}\}$. The Manifold's name changes: $\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\} \Rightarrow \{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{M}\}$).

11.6) $\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\} = \{\mathbb{M}\} \cup \{\mathbb{W}\}$.

The $\{\text{Intrinsic Observer}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}} = \{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}}$ performs an intrinsic analysis of the $\{\text{param.2-Manif. w.b.}\} = \{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}$ and reports her analysis here.

11.7) **$\{\text{Analysis Space}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}} = \{\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}, \{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}}, \{\text{OBIM}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}}, \text{Instr.}\}$.**

11.8) **$\{\text{Reference Space}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}} = \{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}$.**

11.9) **$\{\text{Relations: } \{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}, \{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}}\}$: according to Statement 3.2.**

11.10) **Sheetness.** *By definition*, $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}}$ does not sense Superpositions. Hence $\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}$ appears one-sheeted to her.

11.11) **Sidedness.** $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}}$ travels the entire $\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}$: it appears one-sided.

11.12) **$\{\text{Circular Arrow vector field}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\mathbb{W}\}}$.**

11.12.1) **Initial assumption 1.** $\{\text{Circ. Arr. vector field}\}_{\{\mathbb{M}\}} \equiv [\text{U.N.V. field}] = \nu$.

11.12.2) **Initial Assumption 2.** Smooth { Circ. Arrow vector field }_{M}.

11.12.3) **Initial Assumption 3,** not necessarily, but for quick , easy comparisons:

{ Circ. Arrow }_{(LFRA_{ΔM₀0})_{MW}} = { Circ. Arrow }_{ΔM₀}.

11.12.4) By I. Assumptions 2 & 3: { Circ. Arr. }_{(LFRA_{ut})_{M}} = { Circ. Arr. }_{ΔM_u}; ∀ u.

11.12.5) No { Parametrization }_{W} ⇒ undefined { Circ. Arrow vector field }_{W}, that is assumed = 0.

11.12.6) ¶ ({ M } → { W }) below assures that { LFRA }_{MW} senses

smooth { Transitions: { FWHE }_{M} ←^{in {MW}} { IWHE }_{W} }.

Since: { Adjacency: { FWHE }_{M}, { IWHE }_{W} }, { LFRA }_{MW} restricts herself to consider the **scalar values**:

|| { Circ. Arr. }_{ΔM_f ⊃ { FWHE }_{M}} || = 1 , || { Circ. Arr. }_{ΔW ⊃ { IWHE }_{W}} || = 0.

11.12.7) Different { Circ. Arrow values }, but not opposite in ℤ. That confirms:

Smooth { Transitions: || { Circ. Arrow }_{ΔM_f} || = 1 ⇔ || { Circ. Arrow }_{ΔW} || = 0 }.

11.13) **{M}**. According to { LFRA }_{MW}: { M } from { IWHE }_{M} = { [0 →] ×

[V_[0→]] }_{M} to { FWHE }_{M} = { { → 1 } × [V_{→1}] }_{M}, including them.

11.14) Any state (LFRA_{ut})_{MW} @ ΔM_u, by definition not sensing Superpositions, at the { Reception n.b.h. } = ΔM_u has the { Perception N.B.H. } = ΔM_u.

11.15) **{M} → {W}**. { LFRA }_{MW} can perform, across the { Widthwise Internal

Edge }_{MW}, the { Transition: { FWHE }_{M} ←^{in {MW}} { IWHE }_{W} }.

11.15.1) In other words. Having Touch and the Sensors of her Generalized Curvatures, { Powerful Intrinsic Observer }_{MW} senses: { Smooth Transitions:

{ M } ⊃ { Parametrization }_{M} ←^{in {MW}} { W } ⊃ null Parametrization }_{W} }.

11.15.2) Not smooth in {MW}:

{ Jump Transitions: { FWHE }_{M} ←^{in {Complement Space}} Verso { IWHE }_{M} }.

11.15.3) (LFRA_{ΔM_{→1}m}) @ ΔM_{→1} knows that { FWHE }_{M} is a Marker that precedes the following, non-structured, hence non-marked {W}.

11.16) **{W}**. Any (LFRA_{it})_{MW} @ ΔW_i senses ΔW_i by Touch and Gen. Curvatures Sensors. No capability of sensing a Verso ΔM_u; no possibility of using it as reference. (Eventually a longitudinal coordinate [i] to {W} is applied).

11.16.1) (LFRA_{it})_{MW} @ ΔW_i's { Perception N.B.H. } = { Reception n.b.h. } = ΔW_i.

11.16.2) (LFRA_{it})_{MW} @ ΔW_i's { Perception N.B.H. } of {MW} & Associates.

Case a) { Perception N.B.H. }: { ΔW_i, (LFRA_{it})_{MW} }.

Case b) { Perception N.B.H. }: { ΔW_i, (LFRA_{it'})_{MW}, (OBIM_{it'})_{MW} }.

Case c) { Perception N.B.H. }: { ΔW_i, (LFRA_{it''})_{MW}, Verso (OBIM_{it''})_{MW} }.

11.17) { LFRA }_{MW} in {W} reaches the not marked { FWHE }_{W}. The following { IWHE }_{M} marks the end of {W}.

11.17.1) So that { LFRA }_{MW} has completed one - 2ℒ long - circuit of {MW}.

11.17.2) { LFRA }_{MW} recognizes: { Smooth Transitions: { W } ←^{in {MW}} { M } }.

11.17.3) The above implies: no interposed { Complement Space }_{MW} in the { Glued Zones }_{MW}; { Positional Continuity in the { Glued Zones }_{MW} }.

11.18) **{ Parametric Continuity in {MW} }**. The assessment of Parametric Continuity by the evaluation of partial derivatives at

{ Transitions: $\{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{W\}} \xleftarrow{\text{in } \{MW\}} \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}} \}$,

{ Transitions: $\{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}} \xleftarrow{\text{in } \{MW\}} \{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{W\}} \}$

is not feasible in the above $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{MW\}}$'s 1st analysis, since $\{W\}$ has neither a Maker-adjointed, nor a $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{MW\}}$ -adjointed Parametrization.

A type of **Continuity** is stated by the $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{MW\}}$'s Touch and Gen.Curvature

Sensors - ascertained { Smooth Transitions: $\{M\} \xleftarrow{\text{in } \{MW\}} \{W\} \}$.

11.19) **{W} → {M}**. If $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{MW\}}$ proceeds, she traverses $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}}$, etc.

11.20) **Cyclic {MW}**. After her 1st Circuit of $\{MW\}$ and continuing, $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{MW\}}$ encounters repetitions. The No. of Circuits of $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{MW\}}$ is not in $\{MW\}$, but in $\{\text{Records}\}_{\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{MW\}}} \subset \{\text{Analysis Space}\}_{\{MW\}}$.

11.21) **The { Powerful Intrinsic Observer }_M's ability of sensing out of {M}**.

That is: $\{MW\} = \{M\} \cup \{W\}$ according to the $\{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}_{\{M\}}$.

(Not according to the $\{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}_{\{MW\}}$).

$\{M\}$ is entirely covered by a unique $\{\text{Chart}\}_{\{M\}}$ of a bivariate $\{\text{Parametrization}\}_{\{M\}}$.

In Int $\{M\}$: $\{C^n \text{ Parametric continuity, big } n\}$. $\{W\}$ is not parametrized.

11.21.1) { Final Patch of $\{M\}$ }_{MW} = { FP }_{MW} = { {FP}_M, Verso {FP}_M }.

11.21.2) { Initial Patch of $\{M\}$ }_{MW} = { IP }_{MW} = { {IP}_M, Verso {IP}_M }.

11.21.3) The $\{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}_{\{M\}}$ moves from $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{M\}} \subset \{\text{IP}\}_{\{M\}}$ to $\{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{M\}} \subset \{\text{FP}\}_{\{M\}}$ and no more. In Int $\{M\}$ she senses:

Patches $\{\text{IP}\}_{\{M\}}, \dots, \{\text{FP}\}_{\{M\}}$; { Smooth Transitions: $\{\text{IP}\}_{\{M\}} \xleftarrow{\text{in } \{M\}} \{\text{FP}\}_{\{M\}} \}$.

11.21.4) At $\{\text{FP}\}_{\{M\}}$, $\{\text{IP}\}_{\{M\}}$, she senses locally and can also glance outside $\{M\}$.

11.21.5) The theorist $\{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}_{\{M\}}$: a Surface can have more than one Sheet. Multiple Sheets are intrinsically distinguished by Superposition.

11.21.6) The state ($\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}_{\{\text{FP}\}_f}\}_{\{M\}} @ \{\text{FP}\}_{\{M\}}$, also glancing, has: { Perception N.B.H.s } = { $\{\text{FP}\}_{\{M\}}, \Delta W_0$, Verso $\{\text{IP}\}_{\{M\}}$ }. But ΔW_0 is not sensed by its own, lacking, Parametrization. Anyway it may assume the borrowed Parameter value Verso $\{\text{IP}\}_{\{M\}}$ that renders it perceptible as something different from the $\{\text{IP}\}_{\{M\}}$ that is sensed in another {Reception n.b.h.}.

11.21.7) The state ($\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}_{\{\text{IP}\}_0}\}_{\{M\}} @ \{\text{IP}\}_{\{M\}}$, also glancing, has: { Perception N.B.H.s } = { $\{\text{IP}\}_{\{M\}}, \Delta W_f$, Verso $\{\text{FP}\}_{\{M\}}$ }. But ΔW_f is not sensed by its own, lacking, Parametrization. Anyway it may assume the borrowed Parameter value Verso $\{\text{FP}\}_{\{M\}}$ that renders it perceptible as something different from the $\{\text{FP}\}_{\{M\}}$ that is sensed in another {Reception n.b.h.}.

11.21.8) The $\{\text{Powerful Intrinsic Observer}\}_{\{M\}}$ in her whole trip of $\{M\}$ senses: $\{\text{IP}\}_{\{M\}}$, and ΔW_0 (Verso $\{\text{IP}\}_{\{M\}}$), (not by a unique {Reception n.b.h.}).

$\{\text{FP}\}_{\{M\}}$, and ΔW_f (Verso $\{\text{FP}\}_{\{M\}}$), (not by a unique Reception n.b.h.).

11.21.9) That is not perception of $\{M\}$ only. That leads her to imagine: $\{MW\}$,

{ Superposition: $\{\text{IP}\}_{\{M\}}, \Delta W$ (Verso $\{\text{IP}\}_{\{M\}}$) },

{ Superposition: $\{\text{FP}\}_{\{M\}}, \Delta W$ (Verso $\{\text{FP}\}_{\{M\}}$) }, and two-sheetness of $\{MW\}$.

12 {MM}, {MM}, {TMM}, {TMM}, {LMIRM}, {LMRM}

12.1) {MM}. The Maker got {MM} bending, twisting π rad one Strip {SS}, length \mathcal{L} . His point of view is in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ above the {End Glued Zones}{MM}. Glue: {FWHE}{S2}, {IWHE}{S} and Verso {FWHE}{S}, Verso {IWHE}{S2}.

{End Glued Zones}{MM} = { {FWHE}{M2}, {IWHE}{M} } .

Verso {Intermediate Glued Zones}{MM} = {Verso {FWHE}{M}, Verso {IWHE}{M2}} .

By the {Transformation: {SS} \rightarrow {MM}} the two Sheets i.e. two Sides {S}, {S2} of {SS} became *the unique Side with two in series and superposed Sheets, same chirality*: {M}, {M2} of {MM}. In {MM}: Positional & Parametric Continuity.

12.1.1) The Reader can compare {MM} and the Doubling {DM}. [15], [21], [17].

12.2) {MM}. {LFRA}{MM} analyzes and names {MM} the Maker's {MM}.

12.3) *By definition*, {LFRA}{MM} does not sense Superposition of Sheets. She senses a unique Sheet of {MM}: the one, length $2\mathcal{L}$, in which she travels. Having smooth Transitions in the entire {MM}, not observing another unreachable Side, she senses a unique Side and ignores multi-Sidedness.

12.4) {Relations: {MM}, {LFRA}{MM}}. {LFRA}{MM} remains within the {Intrinsic Boundary}{MM}, without going out of it, without sensing outside it.

12.5) Supposedly {LFRA}{MM} has completed at least one Circuit of {MM}, so knowing {MM}; the following is her report.

12.6) {LFRA}{MM} knows that the {Structure}{MM} with specified Directions & Orientations implies a dissimmetry of {MM}, with a counterpart.

12.7) **Periodicity in the {MM}'s travel.** In the case of continuing her travel in {MM} after her 1st Circuit and performing **n Circuits**, {LFRA}{MM} encounters repetitions in {MM} and its {Structure}{MM}. She recognizes the periodicity of her {MM}'s travel. Obviously, {LFRA}{MM}'s recordings are not in {MM}, but in the {Analysis Space}{MM}.

12.8) Ignoring Thickness, {LFRA}{MM} can't apply Thickness to {MM}.

12.9) **Coorientation: {MM}, {LFRA}{MM}**. {LFRA}{MM}'s Directions & Orientations intervene in the evaluation of {MM}'s Directions & Orientations.

12.9.1) {LFRA}{MM}'s adaptations for her directed & oriented Circuit of {MM}.

a) $(LFRA_{[0 \rightarrow]0})_{\{MM\}} @ \{Initial\ n.b.h.\}_{\{M\}}$'s Aft \rightarrow Front Direction & Orientation, and Left \rightarrow Right Direction & Orientation are equalized to those of the {Initial n.b.h.}{M} $\supset \{[0 \rightarrow] \times [V_{[0 \rightarrow]}]\}_{\{M\}}$. b) Locally, Aft \rightarrow Front Direction & Orientation and Left \rightarrow Right Direction & Orientation, of {MM} and the {LFRA}{MM}'s ones, are kept equal in the {{LFRA}{MM}'s Circuits of {MM}}. c) {Circ. Arrow}{ $(LFRA_{[0 \rightarrow]0})_{\{M\}}$ } = {Circ. Arrow}{Initial n.b.h.}{M}; {Circ. Arrow}{Initial n.b.h.}{M} \in {Circ. Arrow vector field}{MM} that is smooth, since a Side has a smooth {Circ. Arrow vector field}, and {MM} is one-sided.

Hence: {Circ. Arrow}{ $(LFRA_{u,t})_{\{MM\}}$ } = {Circ. Arrow}{ $\Delta_{\{MM\}}_u$ }; $\forall \Delta_{\{MM\}}_u$.

12.10) **Smoothness of {MM} = {M} \cup {M2}**. {LFRA}{MM} recognizes: {M}, {M2} are smoothly directed & oriented lengthwise and widthwise, and smoothly joined.

12.10.1) According to $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\text{MM}\}}$, the $\{\text{MM}\}$'s Smoothness implies:
preferably a single $\{\text{Chart}\}_{\{\text{MM}\}} = \{\text{Chart}\}_{\{\text{M}\}} \cup \{\text{Chart}\}_{\{\text{M2}\}}$.

12.11) **Coordinates for any Lengthwise Curve.**

$[u]_{\{\text{M}\}} = [u]_{\{\text{S}\}}, [u]_{\{\text{M2}\}} = [u]_{\{\text{S2}\}} ; [u]_{\{\text{M}\}} \cup [u]_{\{\text{M2}\}} \rightarrow \text{global } [u]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$.

12.12) **Coordinate along any Ruling Vector.** $[v]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$ like $[v]_{\{\text{M}\}}$.

12.13) **Field $\{\text{Twin Parallel Lengthw. Curves}\}$** = $\{ \{ [\gamma_{-v/2}], [\gamma_{v/2}] \} \}_{\{\text{MM}\}}$.

For $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\text{MM}\}}$: $\{\text{Pair: one left, one right curve. Lengthwise, independent, geodesic, parallel, not self - intersecting, closed, } 2\mathcal{L} \text{ long Curves, with curvature, torsion and cyclic order}\}$ (superposed too according to $\{\text{pLFRA}\}_{\{\text{MM}\}}$). Equal **Orientation C** by $\{\text{Maker-applied Arrows}\}$. Opposite **Orientation I** by $\{\text{Induced Orientation Arrows}\}$. Mutual distance = $v(u)$ on any Vector $[\mathbf{V}_u]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$.

12.13.1) Each $[\gamma_{-v/2}]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$, (similarly each $[\gamma_{v/2}]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$), has a smooth $\{\text{Frenet frame field}\}$, Positional Continuity and Frenet Frame Continuity.

12.13.2) They have their $\{\text{Initial Half Points}\}$ on $[\mathbf{V}_{\{\mathbf{0}\rightarrow\}}]_{\{\text{M}\}} = [\mathbf{V}_{\{\mathbf{0}\rightarrow\}}]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$.

12.13.3) They have their $\{\text{Final Half Points}\}$ on $[\mathbf{V}_{\{\rightarrow\mathbf{1}\}}]_{\{\text{M2}\}} = [\mathbf{V}_{\{\rightarrow\mathbf{0}\}}]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$.

12.13.4) $0 \leq v \leq \ell$. **Generic Twin Par. Len. Curves** $\{ [\gamma_{-v/2}]_{\{\text{MM}\}}, [\gamma_{v/2}]_{\{\text{MM}\}} \}$.

12.13.5) **$\{\text{Centre Twin Parallel Lengthwise Curves}\}$** . One the Left, the other the Right of $[\text{Midline}] = [\gamma_0]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$. $\{ [\gamma_{\{\rightarrow\mathbf{0}\}}]_{\{\text{MM}\}}, [\gamma_{\{\mathbf{0}\rightarrow\}}]_{\{\text{MM}\}} \}$.

12.13.6) **$\{\text{Intrinsic Boundary Twin Parallel Lengthwise Curves}\}_{\{\text{MM}\}}$** = $\{ [\gamma_{BT}]_{\{\text{MM}\}} = \{ [\gamma_{\{B\rightarrow\}}]_{\{\text{MM}\}}, [\gamma_{\{\rightarrow T\}}]_{\{\text{MM}\}} \} \}$.

12.14) **$\{\text{Ruled Surface Vector Field in } \{\text{MM}\}\}$** = $\{ [\mathbf{V}] \}_{\{\text{MM}\}}$.

12.14.1) Generic $[\text{Vector along } \{\text{Ruling } u\}] = [\mathbf{V}_u]_{\{\text{MM}\}} \cdot \|\mathbf{V}_u\| = \ell(u)$.

12.14.2) **$[\text{Initial Half Vector}]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$** = $[\mathbf{V}_{\{\mathbf{0}\rightarrow\}}]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$.

12.14.3) **$[\text{Final Half Vector}]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$** = $[\mathbf{V}_{\{\rightarrow\mathbf{0}\}}]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$.

12.14.4) **Orientation V** of $[\mathbf{V}_u]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$ by $[v]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$:

Bottom \rightarrow Midpoint \rightarrow Top i.e. $B \rightarrow \rightarrow 0 \rightarrow \rightarrow T$.

12.14.5) **Orientation C** of $\{ [\mathbf{V}] \}_{\{\text{MM}\}}$. The field $\{ [\mathbf{V}] \}_{\{\text{MM}\}}$ is cyclically ordered in $\{\text{MM}\}$ by $[u]_{\{\text{M}\}} \rightarrow [u]_{\{\text{M2}\}} \rightarrow [u]_{\{\text{M}\}}$; globally by $[u]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$. [26].

12.14.6) **Orientation C \times V** of $\{ [\mathbf{V}] \}_{\{\text{MM}\}}$: a dictionary order.

12.15) **Angle β** : $[\mathbf{t}], [\mathbf{V}_u]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$. It is defined by the local Curvature and Torsion.

12.15.1) $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\text{MM}\}}$ senses: $\beta_{GZ} = \pm\pi/2$ in the $\{\text{Glued Zones}\}_{\{\text{MM}\}}$. [20].

12.16) **$(\text{LFRA}_{u_t})_{\{\text{MM}\}}$'s $\{\text{Perception N.B.H.s.}\} \supset \{\text{Reception n.b.h.}\}$, no $\{\text{Superposed n.b.h.}\}$.** $(\text{LFRA}_{\{\mathbf{0}\rightarrow\mathbf{0}\}})_{\{\text{MM}\}}$'s $\{\text{Perception N.B.H.}\} \supset \{\text{Reception n.b.h.}\} \supset \{ [\mathbf{0}\rightarrow\mathbf{0}] \times [\mathbf{V}_{\{\mathbf{0}\rightarrow\mathbf{0}\}}] \}_{\{\text{MM}\}}$. $(\text{LFRA}_{\{\rightarrow\mathbf{0}\}f})_{\{\text{MM}\}}$'s $\{\text{Perception N.B.H.}\} \supset \{\text{Reception n.b.h.}\} \supset \{ \{\rightarrow\mathbf{0}\} \times [\mathbf{V}_{\{\rightarrow\mathbf{0}\}}] \}_{\{\text{MM}\}}$.

12.17) **Sequence $\{\text{MM}\}$** is ordered by the lengthwise Coordinate $[u]_{\{\text{MM}\}}$:

$\{ \{ [\mathbf{0}\rightarrow\mathbf{0}] \times [\mathbf{V}_{\{\mathbf{0}\rightarrow\mathbf{0}\}}] \}_{\{\text{MM}\}}, \dots, \{ \{\rightarrow\mathbf{1}\} \times [\mathbf{V}_{\{\rightarrow\mathbf{1}\}}] \}_{\{\text{MM}\}} \cup \cup \{ [\mathbf{1}\rightarrow\mathbf{0}] \times [\mathbf{V}_{\{\mathbf{1}\rightarrow\mathbf{0}\}}] \}_{\{\text{MM}\}}, \dots, \{ \{\rightarrow\mathbf{0}\} \times [\mathbf{V}_{\{\rightarrow\mathbf{0}\}}] \}_{\{\text{MM}\}} \}$.

12.18) **Edges.** The $\{\text{MM}\}$ -confined $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\text{MM}\}}$ can contact, hence senses:

12.18.1) $\{\text{Lengthw. Interior Half Edges}\}_{\{\text{MM}\}} = \{ [\gamma_{\{B\rightarrow\}}]_{\{\text{MM}\}}, [\gamma_{\{\rightarrow T\}}]_{\{\text{MM}\}} \}$.

12.18.2) $\{\text{Widthwise Interior Half Edges}\}$: $\{\text{FWHE}\}_{\{\text{M2}\}} = \|\mathbf{V}_{\{\rightarrow\mathbf{0}\}}\|_{\{\text{MM}\}}$, $\{\text{IWHE}\}_{\{\text{M}\}} = \|\mathbf{V}_{\{\mathbf{0}\rightarrow\mathbf{0}\}}\|_{\{\text{MM}\}}$. They are the terminals of $\{\text{MM}\}$'s $2\mathcal{L}$ length.

But they allow smooth Transitions, hence multiple $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\text{MM}\}}$'s circuits.

12.19) **{Oriented Intrinsic Boundary}** $_{\{\text{MM}\}}$ by $\{\text{Induced Orientation Arrows}\}$:

$$[[\mathbf{V}_{\{\mathbf{o} \rightarrow\}}]_{\{\text{MM}\}} , [\gamma_{\{\rightarrow T\}}]_{\{\text{MM}\}} , - [\mathbf{V}_{\{\rightarrow \mathbf{o}\}}]_{\{\text{MM}\}} , - [\gamma_{\{B \rightarrow\}}]_{\{\text{MM}\}}] .$$

12.19.1) It contains $\{\text{Oriented Intr. Boundary}\}_{\{\text{M}\}}$, $\{\text{Oriented Intr. Boundary}\}_{\{\text{M2}\}}$.

12.20) **Twist**. By her Generalized Curvatures' Sensors, $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\text{MM}\}}$ measures the local Torsion. Then she calculates $\int_{\{\text{M}\}} d\tau$, $\int_{\{\text{M2}\}} d\tau$ of $\{\text{MM}\}$.

12.21) **{Tubular MM}** = $\{\text{TMM}\}$, according to the $\{\text{Maker}\}$ in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$, who builds, and then analyzes it moving longitudinally and around.

12.21.1) He takes a straight Tube, i.e. a cylinder, circular section, \mathcal{L} long, 2ℓ circumference, small ℓ/\mathcal{L} .

12.21.2) He chooses a $\{\text{Plane across the straight Tube's Axis}\} = \{\text{AP}\}$.

12.21.3) $\{\{\text{Tube}\} \cap \{\text{AP}\}\} \rightsquigarrow$ straight $[\text{Lengthwise Lines}]$:

$$[\text{D}] = [\text{DL}] \cup [\text{DR}] , [\text{U}] = [\text{UL}] \cup [\text{UR}] .$$

12.21.4) The $[\text{Lengthwise Lines}]$ demarcate two straight components of $\{\text{Tube}\}$, then colored, each one \mathcal{L} long:

$\{\text{Green Half Tube}\} = \{\text{TM}\}$, with $[\text{Lengthwise Lines}]$: $[\text{DL}]$, $[\text{UL}]$;

$\{\text{Red Half Tube}\} = \{\text{TM2}\}$, with $[\text{Lengthwise Lines}]$: $[\text{DR}]$, $[\text{UR}]$.

12.21.5) He bends, twists π rad, then joins

the $\{\text{TM}\}$'s End Sections, i.e. $\{\text{Glued Zones}\}$: $[\text{IGZ}]_{\{\text{TM}\}}$, $[\text{FGZ}]_{\{\text{TM}\}}$ to

the $\{\text{TM2}\}$'s End Sections, i.e. $\{\text{Glued Zones}\}$: $[\text{FGZ}]_{\{\text{TM2}\}}$, $[\text{IGZ}]_{\{\text{TM2}\}}$.

Each $\{\text{Glued Zone}\}$ a Semicircle ℓ long. Getting:

$$12.21.6) [\text{FGZ}]_{\{\text{TM2}\}} \xleftarrow{\text{smooth Contact (same gen. curvatures) \& Glue}} [\text{IGZ}]_{\{\text{TM}\}} ;$$

$$12.21.7) [\text{FGZ}]_{\{\text{TM}\}} \xleftarrow{\text{smooth Contact (same gen. curvatures) \& Glue}} [\text{IGZ}]_{\{\text{TM2}\}} .$$

12.21.8) The result is: united, bent & twisted, glued at their ends

"Green Section C Half Tube" \cup "Red Section D Half Tube" i.e. $\{\text{TM}\} \cup \{\text{TM2}\}$.

12.21.9) Straight $[\text{Lengthwise Lines}] \rightsquigarrow$ bent & twisted, closed, $2\mathcal{L}$ long

$[\text{Lengthwise Intrinsic Edge}]_{\{\text{TMM}\}} = [\text{LIE}]_{\{\text{TMM}\}} = [\text{LLIHE}]_{\{\text{TMM}\}} \cup [\text{RLIHE}]_{\{\text{TMM}\}}$.

12.21.10) Left of $[\text{LIE}]_{\{\text{TMM}\}}$ i.e. $[\text{Left Lengthwise Intrinsic Half Edge}] =$

$$[\text{LLIHE}]_{\{\text{TMM}\}} = [[L_0 \rightarrow] , \dots , \{ \rightarrow L_M \} [L_M \rightarrow] , \dots , \{ \rightarrow L_0 \}] .$$

12.21.11) Right of $[\text{LIE}]_{\{\text{TMM}\}}$ i.e. $[\text{Right Lengthwise Intrinsic Half Edge}] =$

$$[\text{RLIHE}]_{\{\text{TMM}\}} = [[R_0 \rightarrow] , \dots , \{ \rightarrow R_M \} [R_M \rightarrow] , \dots , \{ \rightarrow R_0 \}] .$$

12.21.12) $\{\text{End Half Points}\}_{\{\text{TMM}\}}$ specify them .

12.21.13) $[\text{LLIHE}]_{\{\text{TMM}\}}$, $[\text{RLIHE}]_{\{\text{TMM}\}}$ have equal $\{\text{Maker-applied Arrows}\}$,

opposite $\{\text{Induced Orientation Arrows}\}$, and are in a smooth Lengthwise Contact.

12.21.14) Structured, $(\mathcal{L} \times 2\ell)$, $\{\text{Outer Side}\}_{\{\text{TMM}\}}$.

$(\mathcal{L} \times 2\ell)$, $\{\text{Inner Side}\}_{\{\text{TMM}\}}$. If detecting properties, the $\{\text{Maker}\}$ recognizes it.

In this case, according to him, $\{\text{TMM}\}$ is two-sided.

12.22) **{TMM}**. $\{\text{LFRA}\}_{\{\text{TMM}\}}$ lies on and analyzes $\{\text{TMM}\} = \{\text{TM}\} \cup \{\text{TM2}\}$.

12.22.1) $\{\text{Outer Side}\}_{\{\text{TMM}\}} \supset \{\text{Chart}\}_{\{\text{TMM}\}} = \{\text{Chart}\}_{\{\text{TM}\}} \cup \{\text{Chart}\}_{\{\text{TM2}\}}$.

She does not sense a $\{\text{Inner Side}\}_{\{\text{TMM}\}}$. Hence one-sided $\{\text{TMM}\}$ for her.

12.22.2) She operates in the $\{\text{Outer Side}\}_{\{\text{TMM}\}}$, on which she can move lengthwise in a full circuit, and also widthwise. Her possible entire widthwise movement makes her analysis equal to the $\{\text{Maker}\}$'s analysis of the $\{\text{Outer Side}\}_{\{\text{TMM}\}}$.

12.23) The Maker may perceive an $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ -immersed, splitted in three pieces-[6]-**Klein Bottle**: a Surface, supposedly here with a circular cross section, that crosses itself with a circular section. It may belong to the following homotopy classes: LR, L'R', for which two of these pieces are Möbius Strips of opposite chirality; LL and RR, for which two of these pieces have the same chirality.

12.24) $\{\text{LMIRM}\} = \{M0\} \cup \{M1\}$. A composition of two Möbius Strips is considered here. The Maker got it by two narrow rectangular structured one-sheeted one-sided Strips, same length \mathcal{L} , width ℓ , direction and orientation; bending, twisting them into an union in series, length $2\mathcal{L}$, of two {Moëbius Strips} of *opposite Chirality* and the same *Direction & Orientation*. The four Terminal Rulings are dubbed {Glued Zones} $_{\{\text{LMIRM}\}}$: $\{\text{IGZ}\}_{\{M0\}}$, $\{\text{FGZ}\}_{\{M0\}}$, $\{\text{IGZ}\}_{\{M1\}}$, $\{\text{FGZ}\}_{\{M1\}}$. (♦) A thin {Complement Space} between $\{\text{FGZ}\}_{\{M1\}} \cup \{\text{IGS}\}_{\{M0\}}$ and Verso $\{\text{FGZ}\}_{\{M0\}} \cup \text{Verso } \{\text{IGZ}\}_{\{M1\}}$. Figure 2.

12.24.1) After its construction, the {Maker} moving in $\{\mathbb{R}^3\}$ around $\{\text{LMIRM}\}$ senses: a) { Smooth Transition: $\{\text{FGZ}\}_{\{M1\}}$, $\{\text{IGZ}\}_{\{M0\}}$ }, $\{M0\}$. { Smooth Transition: $\{\text{FGZ}\}_{\{M0\}}$, $\{\text{IGZ}\}_{\{M1\}}$ }, $\{M1\}$. b) Not obligingly, but by the assumption (♦): b1) { No Self-contact: Verso $\{\text{FGZ}\}_{\{M0\}}$; $\{\text{IGZ}\}_{\{M0\}}$ }. (Correspondingly, in an isolated Möbius Strip, no smooth Transitions between them). b2) { No Self-contact: $\{\text{FGZ}\}_{\{M1\}}$; Verso $\{\text{IGZ}\}_{\{M1\}}$ }. (Correspondingly, in an isolated Möbius Strip, no smooth Transitions between them).

c) $\{\text{LMIRM}\}$ does not pass through itself.

d) In $\{\text{LMIRM}\}$: two {Lengthwise Half Edges} $_{\{\text{LMIRM}\}}$, each one $2\mathcal{L}$ long:

$\{\text{Left LHE}\}_{\{\text{LMIRM}\}} = \{\text{Left LHE}\}_{\{M0\}} \cup \{\text{Left LHE}\}_{\{M1\}}$,

$\{\text{Right LHE}\}_{\{\text{LMIRM}\}} = \{\text{Right LHE}\}_{\{M0\}} \cup \{\text{Right LHE}\}_{\{M1\}}$.

e) Two {Widthwise Internal Half Edges} $_{\{\text{LMIRM}\}}$:

$\{\text{WIHE}\}_{\{M0\}} = \{\text{IGZ}\}_{\{M0\}}$, $\{\text{WFHE}\}_{\{M1\}} = \{\text{FGZ}\}_{\{M1\}}$.

f) {Oriented Intrinsic Boundary} $_{\{\text{LMIRM}\}} =$

$\{\{\text{WIHE}\}_{\{M0\}}, \{\text{Right LHE}\}_{\{\text{LMIRM}\}}, -\{\text{WFHE}\}_{\{M1\}}, -\{\text{Left LHE}\}_{\{\text{LMIRM}\}}\}$.

12.25) $\{\text{LMRM}\}$. The {Powerful Intrinsic Observer} $_{\{\text{LMRM}\}}$ has the ability of sensing superposed sheets. But her abstract analysis reveals no superposition. It reveals $\{\text{LMRM}\}$ with one Sheet / one Side, by (♦) also at the {Glued Zones}; its parametrized $\{M0\}$, $\{M1\}$, the four smooth $\{\text{GZ}\}_{\{\text{LMRM}\}}$, etc.

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Figure 1: $\{LFRA\}$, $\{OBIM\}$ on $\{M\}$; $\{LFRA\}$, Verso $\{OBIM\}$ on $\{MM\}$, $\{S^2\}$.
 $\{LFRA\}$: the heavy quadric. $\{OBIM\}$, Verso $\{OBIM\}$: the pale quadrics.

Figure 2: {LMRM}